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ABSTRACT:

Deliverable D 4.11 provides a description of the **workflow and requirements** to ensure *interoperability for Open Science and Open Publishing Resources*, focusing on the **FAIRification process** in all its aspects.

During the definition and refinement of the workflow and requirements, **close collaboration** with the development of the **Common Semantic Framework within WP4** and the **design of the H2IOSC MarketPlace (WP5)** has, as expected, been essential.

Strong links have also emerged and been consolidated with the **development of the Pilots within WP7** for the centrality of the FAIRification process.

The **workflow**, consisting of **five phases**, is illustrated together with the **requirements specified for each phase**.

Particular attention is paid to the **first phase** and, secondly, to the **second phase** in which the greatest progress has been made and the most significant developments and project results have been achieved.

In general, the main **results** of the workflow and the associated requirements are the construction of the **data model with a FAIR approach** and the design and implementation of the **prototype software for the FAIRification of resources**, to be integrated with the H2IOSC MarketPlace.

Typically, the workflow also includes functional and performance testing of the developed software prototype and its roll-out, monitoring and fine-tuning.

In parallel, a **system for building native FAIR resources and data** is being designed and implemented, to be fully integrated with the aforementioned prototype software to ensure effective interoperability and smooth data exchange.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ABCSI	Biographical Archive of Italian Scientific Culture
AFR	Archive of Renaissance Philosophers
AGB	Giordano Bruno Archive
AGCV	Giulio Cesare Vanini Archive
ATC	Tommaso Campanella Archive
ATSS	Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism
BD	Database of philosophical texts of the modern age
CLERP	Lessico etico-religioso e politico di Tommaso Campanella (edited by Andrea Suggi)
DAPHNET	Digital Archives of PHilosophical Texts on the NET
DDL	Daphnet Digital Library'
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
H2IOSC	Humanities and cultural Heritage Open Science Cloud
LCA	Leibniz's Correspondents and Acquaintances
XML-TEI	eXtensible Markup Language – Text Encoding Initiative
UUID	Universally Unique Identifier

INTRODUCTION

Deliverable D 4.11 provides a description of the **workflow and requirements to ensure interoperability for Open Science and Open Publishing Resources**, focusing on the **FAIRification process** in all its aspects.

During the definition and refinement of the workflow and requirements, **close collaboration** with the development of the **Common Semantic Framework within WP4** and the **design of the H2IOSC MarketPlace (WP5)** has, as expected, been essential.

Strong links have also emerged and been consolidated with the **development of the Pilots within WP7** for the centrality of the FAIRification process.

The **workflow**, consisting of **five phases**, is illustrated below together with the **requirements specified for each phase**.

We will focus in particular on the **first** and the **second phases**, where the greatest progress has been made and the most significant project developments and results have been achieved.

1. FAIRIFICATION PROCESS: WORKFLOW AND REQUIREMENTS

The **workflow** consists of the following steps:

1. **Data collection and analysis**
2. **Data model construction using the FAIR approach**
3. **Software prototype implementation**
4. **Prototype testing**
5. **Roll-out, monitoring and fine tuning.**

The **requirements** for the success of the workflow **are specified for each phase**.

1.1 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The **first phase** includes:

- The collection and mapping of resources and data to be FAIRified;
- The identification of the different types of resources to be subjected to the FAIRification process, with specific details on the formats, characteristics and dimensions to be managed;
- The quantification of the consistency of the data to be processed.

The activities took place within **two exemplary case studies**, in order to focus on and concretely address the **three major common problems** encountered in the Humanities and Cultural Heritage research domains and communities – and clearly highlighted by **WP4** of the H2IOSC project – and subsequently to develop **the related essential theoretical and practical solutions in order to enable multi-level interoperability**:

- Heterogeneous formats and the consequent need for semantic alignment of contents
- Lock-in caused by obsolete platforms and systems
- Lack of long-term sustainability plans.

The **first case study** involved an in-depth analysis of a well-structured range of **databases and resources belonging to ILIESI**, significant both for their typological richness and diversity, and for having been developed over a long period of time: the resources are being subjected to the

FAIRification process within the WP7 – Community pilots: innovative cross-domain services and environments.

The **second case study** concerns the prospective participation in the authorial use of the platform by a number of **candidate research groups that are designing and producing very heterogeneous digital collections**. A general analysis of these collections, in order to define the types of resources that will be managed, has already been carried out and the results will be reported in the coming months.

1.1.1 1ST CASE STUDY: ANALYSIS OF ILIESI DIGITAL COLLECTIONS AND RESOURCES TO BE FAIRIFIED

The aim was to map and analyse the existing ILIESI digital collections in order to draw up a complete and detailed list of the different types of resources to be FAIRified within the H2IOSC project.

The table below lists **the collections available on the ILIESI portal**, highlighting those examined as they are included in the scope of the analysis.

List of Digital Collections

N.	Digital collections	Archive with link to the source	Notes/Sample file
1	Archivio dei filosofi del Rinascimento (Archive of Renaissance philosophers)	AGB ATC AGCV	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aforismi.xml (ATC)
2	Archivio di Testi per la Storia dello Spinozismo (Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism)	ATSS	
3	Archivio Tullio Gregory	ATG	Archive outside the scope of analysis
4	Banca dati di testi filosofici dell'età moderna (Database of philosophical texts of the modern age)	BD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> wolpe2.cod
5	Daphnet	Daphnet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> baumph2.xml gfedeli,+122-1366-1-CE.xml
6	FONTIonline (Online sources)	fonti_online	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> la_genesi_critica_giudizio_kant_prima_introduzione.pdf HoIDVSP.pdf
7	Illness in ConText: Parole di filosofia e orientamento nella pandemia (Illness in ConText: words of philosophy and guidance during the pandemic)	illness_context	

N.	Digital collections	Archive with link to the source	Notes/Sample file
8	Le prime traduzioni della Monadologia di Leibniz	Leibniz	Archive outside the scope of analysis
9	Lessici filosofici dell'età moderna (Early-Modern and Modern Philosophical Lexica)	Lessici	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Alst0.gif Alst_TABLE.csv
10	Lessico delle passioni in età moderna (Lexicon of Early-Modern and Modern Passions)	LessicoPassioni	
11	Opere complete di Giambattista Vico (Giambattista Vico's Complete Works)	DirVico	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 003_009.html 009.jpg
12	Osservatorio Neologico della lingua italiana	ONLI	Archive outside the scope of analysis
13	Prin ILIESI	PRIN	Digital resources from National Research Projects
14	Tradizioni filosofiche e culturali greche della Magna Grecia e della Sicilia antica	CSPA	Archive outside the scope of analysis
15	Vocabolario panlatino di Emodinamica	bdt_pub	Archive outside the scope of analysis

The table below lists **all the types of resources identified** in the survey of digital collections that were examined in detail during this phase.

List of Resource Categories and Types

Resource Category	Resource Type	Object
Collection	Collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bibliographical record
Text	Print	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bibliographical record facsimile critical edition transcript
	Manuscripts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> facsimile critical edition transcript
	Letters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> facsimile critical edition transcript
	Archival documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> archival record
	Journal articles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> codicological record
Terminologies	Lexicon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> lexicographical record transcript

Resource Category	Resource Type	Object
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> dataset
	Vocabulary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> lexicographical record transcript dataset
	Encyclopaedia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> lexicographical record transcript dataset
	Glossary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> lexicographical record transcript dataset
Prosopographies	Biography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> biographical record iconography
Bibliographies	Special Bibliographies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> bibliographical record
	Catalogues and Inventories	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> codicological record

The table has been compiled using the **Glossary** developed by the ILIESI team, the latest version of which can be found in the *Appendix A*.

1.1.1.1 LEXICA

The 'Lexicon' resource type is described below in its current state, with emphasis on its peculiarities and distinctive features.

Lexica are lexicographical works that collect and analyse the vocabulary of various authors, historical periods (from antiquity to the modern age), cultural movements and languages for which a digital transcription has been provided in order to create a freely accessible database. These are works that can cover various disciplines and fields, including philosophy, literature, politics, science, religion and others; a collection of words or vocabulary organised according to specific criteria that can contain definitions, explanations, contextualisations or other types of information related to the lexicon in question.

Among the digital resources on the ILIESI portal, in the field of lexica, we find the collections:

- **Early-Modern and Modern Philosophical Lexica** – The Archive of Early-Modern and Modern Philosophical Lexica aims to document the physiognomy of modern philosophical-scientific culture and is based on a selection of lexicographical texts. It consists of 25 lexica, divided into three main sections: Philosophical, Scientific and Scholarly Lexica in Latin; Philosophical Lexica in Modern Languages; Author's Lexica. All three collections contain digital reproductions of the printed editions of the lexica and a transcription of the entries in each lexicon; for each lexicon there is also a file containing bibliographical and historical information, as well as a file on the author and his writings.
- **Lexicon of Early-Modern and Modern Passions** – The archive consists of 3 foundational philosophical treatises by Early Modern authors on the subject of passions. The texts have been organized so as to allow a comparative/synoptic presentation of the respective definitions of the passions.

Further works are contained within the following archives:

- **Daphnet Digital Library**, a platform of secondary sources that offers a selection of critical contributions centred on the texts contained in the portal Daphnet – Digital Archives of Philosophical texts on the NET (dedicated to the collection, preservation and dissemination of philosophical texts of historical and scientific relevance in digital format). The contributions (mostly taken from the catalogue of printed volumes and ILIESI journals) are linked to the texts included in the Daphnet platforms and to the articles published in the international journal *Lexicon Philosophicum*;
- **Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism – ATSS**, a digital platform that collects multilingual philosophical texts by various authors, images and documentary material, with the aim of providing a tool for reading and deepening one's knowledge of the philosophy and influence of Baruch Spinoza, one of the great rationalists of the 17th century. The 'Lexica' section contains lemmata from encyclopaedic works and specialised lexica on Spinoza

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	de Berlemont, Noël	<i>Colloquia et dictionariolum octo linguarum</i>
2	Binnart, Martin	<i>Biglotton amplificatum</i>
3	Calepio, Ambrogio	<i>Linguarum novem dictionarium</i>
4	D'Aquin, Philippe	<i>Dictionarium absolutissimum Hebraeo-Chaldaeo-Talmudico-Rabbinicum</i>
5	Franciosini, Lorenzo	<i>Vocabolario italiano, e spagnolo</i>
6	Hornkens, Heinrich	<i>Recueil de dictionnaires françoys, espaignolz et latin</i>
7	Richter, Gustav Theodor	<i>Spinozas philosophische Terminologie</i>
8	Scapula, Ioannes	<i>Lexicon Graeco-Latinum</i>
9	Schrevel, Cornelis	<i>Lexicon manuale Graeco-Latinum et Latino-Graecum</i>

- **Archive of Renaissance Philosophers – Section Tommaso Campanella**. It comprehends the *Ethico-religious and political lexicon of Tommaso Campanella* (CLERP), edited by Andrea Suggi, a lexicographical research project dedicated to exploring and documenting the specific vocabulary used by Tommaso Campanella in his most important works in Italian. CLERP is an important contribution to lexicographical and historical-philosophical research. The lexicon aims to clarify the ethical-religious and political concepts developed by Tommaso Campanella in the context of the Renaissance and Early-Modern period, thus facilitating a better understanding of his work and his influence on European culture. It also provides a solid basis for further study.

Data sources

As mentioned above, the lexica can be traced back to five main archives:

- *Lexica*, corresponding to the section 'Early-Modern and Modern Philosophical Lexica' (<https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/Lessici/>);
- *LessicoPassioni*, corresponding to the section 'Early-Modern and Modern Passions' (<https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/LessicoPassioni/index-passioni.php?pagina=home>);
- *DDL*, corresponding to the section 'Daphnet Digital Library' (<https://scholarlysource.lexicon.cnr.it/ojs/index.php/DDL>);

- ATSS, corresponding to the section 'Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism' (https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/spinoza/home_spinoza.html);
- ATC, corresponding to the 'Tommaso Campanella' Section within the digital resource 'Archive of Renaissance Philosophers' (https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/ATC/index_campanella.php).

Structure and formats

Depending on the discipline or field, the structure and format of a lexicon may vary, but in general a lexicon includes several basic components, which are listed below:

- a biographical schema with possible hypertext links to other resources and an image of the author;
- a bibliographical schema with possible hypertext links to other resources;
- an index of the work;
- a digital edition (image or text) consisting of a title page and the pages that make up the work;
- a list of entries, i.e. individual entries or lemmata present;
- a list of occurrences, i.e. references to the number of times a word or phrase appears in the work;
- a list of annotations, which refers to additional notes for clarification or further information.

The various components mentioned above are available in the following formats.

Components	Format	Sample
Biographical schema	• text (html)	Alsted
Bibliographical schema	• text (html)	Compendium lexici philosophici (1626)
Index of the work	• text (html)	see Compendium lexici philosophici, Alsted
List of the entries	• text (html)	see Compendium lexici philosophici, Alsted
List of occurrences	• text (html)	descartes-passions.php
List of annotations	• text (html)	descartes-passions.php
Digital edition	• jpg • gif • text (html)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chau05nn.jpg • Alst0.gif • descartes-passions.php

Metadata

The metadata of a lexicon can include a variety of information describing the content, structure and context of the lexicon itself.

The main metadata identified can be divided into

- **Collection** (primary resource): a category that collects and organises a set of items with common characteristics (in this case, a lexicon);
- **Biographical schema** (secondary resource): a document that gathers the main data and information about the author of a work in order to contextualise his activity;
- **Lexicographical schema** (secondary resource): a document containing the main data relating to a lexicographical work, useful for identifying and describing it in a bibliographical context.

Number and size

Below is a summary table to collect, for each collection, information such as the number and size in terms of number of works, pages and size of the file(s) relating to the lexica.

N.	Collection	Section	Number of works
1	Early-Modern and Modern Philosophical Lexica	Philosophical, scientific and erudite lexica in Latin	21
		Philosophical lexica in European modern languages	2
		Author's lexicon	2
2	Early-Modern and Modern Passions	-	3
3	Archive of the Renaissance philosophers	Lexicon (Tommaso Campanella)	1
4	Daphnet Digital Library	Sources/Lexica	28
5	Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism	Archive/Lexica	9
<i>Total</i>			<i>66</i>

1.1.1.2 TEXTS

The 'Text' resource type is described below in its current state, with emphasis on its peculiarities and distinctive features.

Text is a work that conveys a message or information, structured according to linguistic rules and with a precise communicative intent.

They can be divided into different types, depending on their content and purpose:

- **Philosophical text:** deals with themes related to the reflection on fundamental concepts such as truth, ethics, knowledge and existence;
- **Political text:** deals with topics regarding the organisation of society, power, laws and the dynamics of government;
- **Religious text:** discusses spiritual, doctrinal or moral questions related to religious beliefs and faith practices;
- **Literary text:** is oriented towards artistic and creative expression, including poetry, novels and short stories;
- **Scientific text:** focuses on the presentation of scientific research and discoveries, using precise technical language;
- **Legal text:** presents rules, laws or regulations related to the legal system.

On the ILIESI portal, among the digital resources available for the study of texts, users can find the following sections:

- Database of Early-Modern and Modern philosophical texts,
- Daphnet – Digital Archives of Philosophical Texts on the NET,
- Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism,
- Archive of Renaissance philosophers,
- Giambattista Vico's Complete Works,
- Online Sources – Documentary support for ILIESI publications,
- ILIESI PRIN.

Database of philosophical texts of the modern age

The archive Database of philosophical texts of the modern age contains an archive of philosophical and scientific texts from the 17th and 18th centuries; in most cases these are texts printed in ancient editions, in some cases accompanied by a photographic reproduction of the original text.

It consists of **127** works divided into four main sections:

List of works in Latin (68)

N.	Author	Title
1	Bacon, Francis	<i>De dignitate et augmentis scientiarum libri IX</i>
2	Bacon, Francis	<i>Historia vitae et mortis</i>
3	Bacon, Francis	<i>Novum organum, sive indicia vera de interpretatione naturae</i>
4	Baumgarten, Alexander Gottlieb	<i>Aesthetica</i>
5	Baumgarten, Alexander Gottlieb	<i>Meditationes philosophicae de nonnullis ad poema pertinentibus</i>
6	Bruno, Giordano	<i>Camoeracensis Acrotismus seu rationes articulorum physicorum</i>
7	Bruno, Giordano	<i>Summa terminorum metaphysicorum</i>
8	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>De sensu rerum, et magia</i>
9	Clauberg, Johann	<i>De cognitione Dei et nostri, quatenus naturali rationis lumine, secundum veram philosophiam, potest comparari, exercitationes centum</i>
10	Descartes, René	<i>Meditationes de prima philosophia, in qua Dei existentia et animae immortalitas demonstratur...</i>
11	Descartes, René	<i>Principia philosophiae</i>
12	Descartes, René	<i>Regulae ad directionem ingenii</i>
13	Galilei, Galileo	<i>De motu</i>
14	Galilei, Galileo	<i>De motu accelerato</i>
15	Galilei, Galileo	<i>De motu locali</i>
16	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Juvenilia</i>
17	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Sidereus nuncius</i>
18	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Theoremata</i>
19	Gassendi, Pierre	<i>Dissertationes en forme de paradoxes contre les aristotéliens (Exercitationes paradoxicae adversus Aristoteles)</i>
20	Genovesi, Antonio	<i>Elementa metaphysicae mathematicum in morem adornata... Pars prior</i>
21	Genovesi, Antonio	<i>Elementa metaphysicae mathematicum in morem adornata... Pars secunda</i>
22	Genovesi, Antonio	<i>Elementa metaphysicae mathematicum in morem adornata... Pars tertia</i>
23	Genovesi, Antonio	<i>Elementorum artis logicocriticae libri V</i>

N.	Author	Title
24	Geulincx, Arnold	<i>Ethica</i>
25	Geulincx, Arnold	<i>Metaphysica</i>
26	's Gravesande, Willem Jacob van	<i>Introductio ad philosophiam, metaphysicam et logicam continens</i>
27	Groot, Huig	<i>De jure belli ac pacis libri tres</i>
28	Herbert, Edward	<i>De veritate, prout distinguitur a revelatione, a verisimili, a possibili, & a falso</i>
29	Hobbes, Thomas	<i>Elementorum philosophiae sectio prima De corpore</i>
30	Hobbes, Thomas	<i>Elementorum philosophiae sectio secunda De homine</i>
31	Hobbes, Thomas	<i>Elementorum philosophiae sectio tertia, De cive</i>
32	Kant, Immanuel	<i>De mundi sensibilis atque intelligibilis forma et principiis. Dissertatio...</i>
33	Kant, Immanuel	<i>Meditationum quarundam de igne succincta delineatio</i>
34	Kant, Immanuel	<i>Metaphysicae cum geometria iunctae usus in philosophia naturali, cuius specimen I. continet monadologiam physicam</i>
35	Kant, Immanuel	<i>Principiorum primorum cognitionis metaphysicae nova dilucidatio</i>
36	Kepler, Johannes	<i>Harmonices mundi libri V</i>
37	Komenský, Jan Amos	<i>Pansophiae preludeum [Prodromus pansophiae]</i>
38	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Brevis demonstratio erroris memorabilis Cartesii et aliorum circa legem naturalem, secundum quam volunt a Deo eandem semper quantitatem motus conservari, qua et in re mechanica abuntur</i>
39	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Causa Dei asserta per justitiam ejus, cum caeteris ejus perfectionibus cunctisque actionibus conciliatam</i>
40	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>De causa gravitatis, et defensio sententiae auctoris de veris naturae legibus contra Cartesianos</i>
41	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>De geometria recondita et analysi indivisibilium atque infinitorum</i>
42	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>De ipsa natura sive de vi insita actionibusque creaturarum, pro dynamicis suis confirmandis illustrandisque</i>
43	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>De legibus naturae et vera aestimatione virium motricium contra Cartesianos</i>
44	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>De primae philosophiae emendatione, et de notione substantiae</i>
45	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Meditationes de cognitione, veritate et ideis</i>
46	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Nova methodus pro maximis et minimis, itemque tangentibus, quae nec fractas nec irrationales</i>

N.	Author	Title
		<i>quantitates moratur, et singulare pro illis calculi genus</i>
47	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Specimen dynamicum pro admirandis naturae legibus circa corporum vires et mutuas actiones detegendis et ad suas causas revocandis. Pars I.</i>
48	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Tentamen de motuum coelestium causis</i>
49	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Principia philosophiae</i>
50	More, Henry	<i>Enchiridion ethicum, praecipua moralis philosophiae rudimenta complectens</i>
51	More, Henry	<i>Enchiridion metaphysicum. Sive, de rebus incorporeis</i>
52	Newton, Isaac	<i>Philosophiae naturalis principia mathematica</i>
53	Pufendorf, Samuel	<i>De jure naturae et gentium, libri octo</i>
54	Spinoza, Baruch	<i>Ethica ordine geometrico demonstrata</i>
55	Spinoza, Baruch	<i>Tractatus de intellectus emendatione, et de via, qua optime in veram rerum cognitionem dirigitur</i>
56	Spinoza, Baruch	<i>Tractatus theologico-politicus continens dissertationes aliquot, quibus ostenditur libertatem philosophandi non tantum salva pietate, & reipublicae pace posse concedi: sed eandem nisi cum pace reipublicae, ipsaque pietate tolli non posse</i>
57	Spinoza, Baruch	<i>Adnotationes ad Tractatum theologico-politicum</i>
58	Tschirnhaus, Ehrenfried Walter von	<i>Medicina mentis, sive artis inveniendi praecepta generalia</i>
59	Vico, Giambattista	<i>De antiquissima Italorum sapientia ex linguae Latinae originibus eruenda libri tres</i>
60	Vico, Giambattista	<i>De constantia iurisprudens liber alter</i>
61	Vico, Giambattista	<i>De nostri temporis studiorum ratione</i>
62	Vico, Giambattista	<i>De universi iuris uno principio et fine uno liber unus</i>
63	Vico, Giambattista	<i>Notae in duos libros, alterum de uno universi iuris principio etc., alterum de constantia iurisprudens</i>
64	Wolff, Christian	<i>Cosmologia generalis, methodo scientifica pertractata, qua ad solidam, in primis Dei atque naturae, cognitionem via sternitur</i>
65	Wolff, Christian	<i>Discursus praeliminaris de philosophia in genere, in Philosophia rationalis sive logica, methodo scientifica pertractata et ad usum scientiarum atque vitae aptata. Praemittitur Discursus praeliminaris de philosophia in genere</i>
66	Wolff, Christian	<i>Philosophia prima, sive ontologia, methodo scientifica pertractata, qua omnis cognitionis humanae principia continentur</i>

N.	Author	Title
67	Wolff, Christian	<i>Psychologia empirica, methodo scientifica pertractata, qua ea, quae de anima humana indubia experientiae fide constant, continentur et ad solidam universae philosophiae practicae ac theologiae naturalis tractationem via sternitur</i>
68	Wolff, Christian	<i>Psychologia rationalis methodo scientifica pertractata, qua ea, quae de anima humana indubia experientiae fide innotescunt, per essentiam et naturam animae explicantur, et ad intimiorem naturae ejusque autoris cognitionem profutura proponuntur</i>

List of works in English (21)

N.	Author	Title
1	Bacon, Francis	<i>The Two Books of Francis Bacon of the Proficience and Advancement of Learning Divine and Humane</i>
2	Berkeley, George	<i>Alciphron, or the minute philosopher in seven dialogues, containing An Apology for the Christian Religion...</i>
3	Berkeley, George	<i>A Treatise Concerning the Principles of Human Knowledge</i>
4	Clarke, Samuel	<i>A demonstration of the Being and Attributes of God : more Particularly in Answer to Mr. Hobbs, Spinoza, and their Followers...</i>
5	Clarke, Samuel	<i>A Discourse concerning the Unchangeable Obligations of Natural Religion and the Truth and Certainty of the Christian Revelation...</i>
6	Collins, Anthony	<i>A discourse of free-thinking...</i>
7	Hartley, David	<i>Observations on Man, his Frame, his Duty, and his Expectations</i>
8	Hobbes, Thomas	<i>Leviathan, or the Matter, Form, and Power of a Commonwealth Ecclesiastical and Civil</i>
9	Hume, David	<i>An Enquire concerning Human Understanding</i>
10	Hutcheson, Francis	<i>An Inquire into the Original of our Ideas of Beauty and Virtue</i>
11	Mandeville, Bernard de	<i>The Fable of the Bees : or Private Vices, Publick Benefits</i>
12	Reid, Thomas	<i>Inquire into the Human Mind</i>
13	Shaftesbury, Antony Ashley Cooper, Earl of	<i>An Inquire Concerning Virtue or Merit</i>
14	Shaftesbury, Antony Ashley Cooper, Earl of	<i>A Letter concerning Enthusiasm to my Lord</i>

N.	Author	Title
15	Shaftesbury, Antony Ashley Cooper, Earl of	<i>Miscellaneous Reflections on the Preceding Treatise, etc..</i>
16	Shaftesbury, Antony Ashley Cooper, Earl of	<i>Sensus Communis : an Essay on the Freedom of Wit and Humour</i>
17	Shaftesbury, Antony Ashley Cooper, Earl of	<i>The Moralist, a Philosophical Rhapsody</i>
18	Shaftesbury, Antony Ashley Cooper, Earl of	<i>Soliloquy or Advice to an Author</i>
19	Smith, Adam	<i>The theory of moral sentiments</i>
20	Toland, John	<i>Christianity not Misterious : or a Treatise Shewing, That there is nothing in the Gospel Contrary to Reason, nor above it : and that no Christian Doctrine can be properly call'd Amystery</i>
21	Toland, John	<i>Letters to Serena</i>

List of works in French (7)

N.	Author	Title
1	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Principes de la philosophie ou Monadologie</i>
2	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Discourse de Métaphysique</i>
3	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Essais de Théodicée</i>
4	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Essais de Théodicée. Reflexions sur l'ouvrage que M. Hobbes a publié en Anglois, de la Liberté, de la Necessité et di Hazare</i>
5	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Essais de Théodicée. Remarques sur le Livre de l'origine du mal, publié depuis peu en Angleterre</i>
6	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Principes de la nature et de la Grace, fondés en raison</i>
7	Leibniz, Gottfried Wilhelm	<i>Systeme nouveau de la nature et de la communication, des substances, aussi bien que de l'union qu'il y a entre l'ame et le corps</i>

List of works in Italian (31)

N.	Author	Title
1	Bruno, Giordano	<i>La cena de le Ceneri. Descritta in cinque dialogi per quattro interlocutori con tre considerazioni circa doi soggetti. All'unico refugio delle muse l'illustrissimo Michel di Castelnovo</i>
2	Bruno, Giordano	<i>De la causa, principio et uno. A l'illustrissimo signor di Mauvissiero</i>
3	Bruno, Giordano	<i>De l'infinito universo e mondi. All'illustrissimo signor di Mauvissiero</i>

N.	Author	Title
4	Bruno, Giordano	<i>Spaccio de la bestia trionfante proposto da Giove, effettuato dal Consiglio, rivelato da Mercurio, recitato da Sofia, udito da Saulino, registrato dal Nolano</i>
5	Bruno, Giordano	<i>Cabala del cavallo pegaseo con l'aggiunta dell'asino cillenico</i>
6	Bruno, Giordano	<i>De gli eroici furori</i>
7	Galilei, Galileo	<i>La Bilancetta...</i>
8	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Breve istruzione all'architettura militare...</i>
9	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Considerazioni circa l'opinione copernicana...</i>
10	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Della forza della percossa</i>
11	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Dialogo sopra i due massimi sistemi del mondo</i>
12	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Difesa contro le calunnie di Baldassarre Capra</i>
13	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Discorsi e dimostrazioni matematiche intorno a due scienze nuove</i>
14	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Discorso del flusso e riflusso del mare</i>
15	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Discorso intorno alle cose che stanno sull'acqua</i>
16	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Istoria e dimostrazioni intorno alle macchie solari</i>
17	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Lettera a Don Benedetto Castelli</i>
18	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Lettera a Jacopo Mazzoni</i>
19	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Lettera a Tolomeo Nozzolini</i>
20	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Lettera al Principe Leopoldo di Toscana</i>
21	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Lettere a Madama Cristina di Lorena</i>
22	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Lettere a Monsignor Piero Dini</i>
23	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Le Mecaniche</i>
24	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Nuovo trovato del prendere la longitudine</i>
25	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Operazioni del compasso geometrico e matematico</i>
26	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Proposta della longitudine</i>
27	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Raccolta di quelle cognizioni che a perfetto cavalier....</i>
28	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Risposta alle opposizioni di L. Delle Colombe</i>
29	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Il Saggiatore</i>
30	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Trattato della sfera ovvero cosmografia</i>
31	Galilei, Galileo	<i>Trattato di fortificazione</i>

Daphnet – Digital Archives of PHilosophical Texts on the NET

On the ILIESI portal, among the digital resources available for the study of philosophical texts in the early modern age, the section 'Daphnet – Digital Archives of PHilosophical Texts on the NET' provides access to the 'Modern Philosophy' platform and the 'Daphnet Digital Library'.

The 'Modern Philosophy' platform consists of two main sections:

- Documentation (Edition) – It contains 53 works divided into 7 sections by author, listed below:
 - Baumgarten (1),
 - Bruno (8),
 - Descartes (5),
 - Kant (4),
 - Leibniz (16),
 - Spinoza (4),
 - Vico (15).
- Archive – It contains 108 works divided into 8 sections by author, listed below:
 - Baumgarten (2),
 - Bruno (8),
 - Descartes (5),
 - Kant (4),
 - Leibniz (25)
 - Locke (2),
 - Spinoza (4),
 - Vico (59).

The ‘Daphnet Digital Library’ is the platform of secondary sources offering a selection of critical contributions centred on the texts contained in the Daphnet portal. The texts are included in a main section called ‘Sources’, which contains a vast range of materials essential for the study of philosophy, divided into:

- ILIESI Proceedings – Where users can explore the contributions already published in the proceedings dedicated to the history of terminology, originally published by Olschki.
- Book Collection – In this section, users can find more about two important contributions to the study of ancient philosophy: *Giannantoni G., Socratis et Socraticorum reliquiae, volumen IV, Bibliopolis, Napoli 1983-1985; Spinelli E., Questioni scettiche. Letture introduttive al pirronismo antico, Lithos, Roma 2005*. Both texts integrate the Daphnet collections offering valuable resources for those who wish to explore and understand more deeply the philosophical traditions of Socrates and ancient scepticism.

Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism

The “Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism – ATSS” is a digital platform that collects multilingual philosophical texts by various authors, as well as images and documentary materials, with the aim of providing an ample toolset for reading and deepening the knowledge of the philosophy and influence of the 17th-century Dutch philosopher Baruch Spinoza. The texts can be found in the main section ‘Archive’, where users can find the following categories:

- Spinoza, Works – This section contains the collected works of Spinoza, taken from the edition *Opera* (1972), edited by Carl Gebhardt on behalf of the Heidelberg Academy of Sciences. Each work is accompanied by detailed information on its history, influence and fortune. In addition, a brief bio-bibliographical note is provided, complete with additional annotations relating to the specific work.

- Spinoza's private library – This section presents the books owned by the philosopher Spinoza, according to the notarial inventory drawn up on 2 March 1677. This collection of books is published on the basis of an unpublished document and also includes detailed biographical and bibliographical notes, as well as an introduction by A. J. Servaas van Rooijen. The section is divided into two main parts in order to access the texts of Spinoza's library:
 - List of books: contains an alphabetical list of Spinoza's texts, with abbreviated titles. Each entry contains links to access the detailed file and online material, divided by type (text, title page, etc.);
 - Notarial inventory of Spinoza's library (2 March 1677): lists the 161 volumes of Spinoza's library, ordered according to the executor's criteria, probably compiled by Jan van Rieuwertsz. The notarial inventory was reported in A. J. Servaas van Rooijen, *Inventaire des livres formant la bibliothèque de Bénédicte Spinoza* (1888).
- Texts on Spinoza and the history of Spinozism – In this section users'll find texts about Spinoza, the controversy surrounding his ideas, and the history of Spinozism.

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	Abbadie, Jacques	<i>Traité de la vérité de la religion chrétienne. Première partie. Seconde édition, revue, corrigée, et augmentée.</i>
2	de Versé, Noël Aubert	<i>L'impie conuaincu, ou Dissertation contre Spinoza</i>
3	Batelier, Jacob	<i>Vindiciae Miraculorum</i>
4	Budde, Johann Franz	<i>Dissertatio philosophica de Spinozismo ante Spinoza</i>
5	Dürr, Johannes Conrad	<i>Actus panegyricus</i>
6	Jenichen, Gottlob Friedrich	<i>Historia Spinozismi Leenhofiani</i>
7	Kortholt, Christian	<i>De tribus impostoribus magnis liber</i>
8	Kuffler, Abraham Johannes	<i>Specimen artis ratiocinandi</i>
9	Kuyper, Frans	<i>Arcana atheismi revelata</i>
10	de La Court, Pieter	<i>De jure ecclesiasticorum, liber singularis</i>
11	Luchi, Bonaventura	<i>Spinozismi Syntagma</i>
12	Richter, Gustav Theodor	<i>Spinozas philosophische Terminologie</i>
13	Stoupe, Jean-Baptiste	<i>La religione degli Olandesi</i>
14	Wittichius, Christophorus	<i>Anti-Spinoza sive examen ethices</i>
15	Wolff, Christian	<i>De Paganismo, Manichaeismo, Spinosismo et Epicureismo</i>
16	Wolff, Christian	<i>Herrn Christian Wolfs Widerlegung der Sittenlehre B. v. S.</i>

Archive of Renaissance philosophers

The archive aims to provide a vast repertoire of resources, making available text transcriptions, original prints, lexicographical and bibliographical tools, historical documents, testimonies, translations, critical studies and other materials of great value. The project aims to assist scholars, researchers and enthusiasts in their exploration of the works and ideas of key figures of the late Renaissance and early modern periods. At present, the archive is dedicated to three very important thinkers: Giordano Bruno, a philosopher and cosmologist whose theories on the infinity of the universe challenged the traditional conceptions of his time; Tommaso Campanella, known for his utopian works and his contributions to political and religious philosophy; and Giulio Cesare Vanini, a libertine philosopher who provoked controversy for his critical views on religion and metaphysics. The archive not only preserves the intellectual heritage of these thinkers, but also facilitates new research and in-depth studies, promoting a deeper understanding of their ideas and the historical context in which they operated.

Giordano Bruno – The Giordano Bruno Archive (AGB) is a platform dedicated to the preservation, study and dissemination of the works and thought of Giordano Bruno, the Italian philosopher and cosmologist known for his theories on the infinity of the universe and the plurality of worlds. This archive is an important resource for those wishing to explore Bruno's influence on modern scientific and philosophical thought. Through a vast collection of documents, manuscripts, original prints and critical studies, the Archive facilitates an in-depth understanding of Bruno's revolutionary ideas and their lasting impact. It is made up of several subsections: Italian texts, Latin texts, Manuscripts, Translations.

Tommaso Campanella – The Tommaso Campanella Archive (ATC) is a specialised resource dedicated to the study and dissemination of the works and thought of Tommaso Campanella. He was one of the most influential philosophers of the Italian Renaissance, known for his utopian works and his contributions to political and religious philosophy. The Archive is therefore a fundamental resource for understanding the Renaissance and the intellectual contribution of one of its greatest thinkers. Its rich collection and related activities provide valuable support for research and teaching in the history of philosophy and ideas. It consists of various types of documents, including: Italian texts, Latin texts, Manuscripts, Letters.

Giulio Cesare Vanini – The Giulio Cesare Vanini Archive (AGCV) is a resource dedicated to the promotion and dissemination of the work of Giulio Cesare Vanini, a libertine philosopher of the early 17th century, known for his critical positions towards religion and traditional metaphysics. The Archive offers a wide range of materials, including transcriptions of texts, original prints, translations, historical documents and critical studies. This archive is essential for those wishing to deepen their knowledge of Vanini's thought and the intellectual context in which he operated, and to promote a better understanding of his contribution to the philosophy and culture of his time. It contains various types of documents, including two Latin texts.

Giambattista Vico's Complete Works

Le opere complete di Giambattista Vico is a digital platform dedicated to the collection, preservation and dissemination of historical critical editions of Giambattista Vico's philosophical opus in digital format.

- The platform includes 8 digital reproductions of works available in JPG and HTML formats, each focusing on different themes such as education, rhetoric, history and human culture, which reflect Giambattista Vico's contribution to philosophy. These works are taken from various volumes edited by Fausto Nicolini and belong to the series 'Scrittori d'Italia' (Writers of Italy), a collection that aims to make available the complete works of important Italian authors.

N.	Author	Title
1	Vico, Giambattista	<i>Le Orazioni inaugurali, il De Italorum sapientia e le Polemiche</i>
2	Vico, Giambattista	<i>Il Diritto universale</i>
3	Vico, Giambattista	<i>La Scienza nuova prima</i>
4	Vico, Giambattista	<i>La Scienza nuova seconda</i>
5	Vico, Giambattista	<i>L'Autobiografia, il Carteggio e le Poesie varie</i>
6	Vico, Giambattista	<i>Scritti storici</i>
7	Vico, Giambattista	<i>Scritti vari e Pagine sparse</i>
8	Vico, Giambattista	<i>Versi d'occasione e Scritti di scuola</i>

Online Sources – Documentary support for ILIESI publications

The 'Online Sources – Documentary Support for ILIESI Publications' archive is a digital platform consisting of various types of documents, such as texts, images, audio or video recordings, referred to in an article, a book, a report by a researcher of the Institute or by scholars who have collaborated with the Institute. The documents are included in the main 'Sources' section.

- **Sources** – This section contains a collection of documents useful for the study of philosophy. Each document contains a bibliography (author, title of the work and year of publication) and for each document there is a related work that refers to the main one. The archive currently consists of 8 works, listed below (primary sources are listed in bold):

N.	Author	Title
1	Hohenemser, Rudolf Ernst (Rolf)	<i>La genesi della Critica del Giudizio di Kant e la Prima introduzione</i>
2	Biscuso, M. and Hohenegger, H.	<i>Rolf Hohenemser e la Prima Introduzione alla Critica del Giudizio</i>
3	Holste, Lukas	<i>Dissertatio de vita et scriptis Porphyrii philosophi</i>
4	Varani, Giovanna	<i>Lucas Holstenius: un intellettuale europeo della prima età moderna, studioso di Altertumswissenschaft fra umanesimo e controriforma.</i>

5	Martini, Cornelius	<i>Disputationum logicarum adversus Ramistas (1594 ed.)</i>
6	Pozzo, Riccardo	<i>Adversus Ramistas. Kontroversen über die Natur der Logik am Ende der Renaissance</i>
7	Martini, Cornelius	<i>Disputationum logicarum adversus Ramistas (1596 ed.)</i>
8	Pozzo, Riccardo	<i>op. cit.</i>
9	Martini, Cornelius	<i>Disputationum metaphysicarum secunda de subiecto metaphysicae</i>
10	Pozzo, Riccardo	<i>op. cit.</i>

ILIESI PRIN – The body-soul problem in the light of ethics

The archive 'ILIESI PRIN – The Body-Soul Problem in the Light of Ethics' is a project that focuses on the publication of studies, texts and a collective volume, on the organisation of seminars and a final conference, and on the creation of a documentation website. The core of the project is the analysis of philosophical works from the 15th to the 18th centuries, including those of Marsilio Ficino, Giordano Bruno and Giambattista Vico, in order to explore the theme of the relationship between the soul and the body. In addition, ecclesiastical censures on philosophical texts of the time are also published. The aim is therefore to explore how the relationship between soul and body influences moral reflection, touching on areas such as anthropology, epistemology, metaphysics and cosmology.

The Archive consists of several subsections, including:

- **Hypertext** – The ILIESI PRIN archive aims to create a hypertextual collection with the title 'The body-soul problem in the light of ethics between the Renaissance and the 18th century: Texts – Thematic Paths – Terminology – Censorship'. This collection includes writings by authors such as Marsilio Ficino, Leone Ebreo, Giordano Bruno and Giambattista Vico, and is based on philosophical works from the late 15th century to the first decades of the 18th century. The archive currently consists of 5 works listed below:

N.	Author	Title
1	Ebreo, Leone	<i>Dialoghi d'amore</i>
2	Ficino, Marsilio	<i>El libro dell'Amore</i>
3	Bruno, Giordano	<i>De gli eroici furori</i>
4	Vico, Giambattista	<i>Scienza Nuova</i>
5	Spruit, Leen	<i>The Controversy over the Animal Soul in Roman Censorship</i>

- **Publications** – This section contains a collection of the full texts of the reports presented at the ILIESI PRIN seminars. The archive currently consists of 8 works listed below:

N.	Author	Title
1	Canone, Eugenio	<i>Anima-corpo alla luce dell'etica. Antichi e moderni</i>
2	Guidi, Simone	<i>Marin Cureau De La Chambre: istinto, immaginazione, innatismo</i>
3	Puccini, Francesca	<i>La ricerca della perfezione fisica e morale nell'antropologia di Helvétius</i>
4	Raimondi, Francesco Paolo	<i>Per un lessico di Giulio Cesare Vanini: il rapporto anima-corpo e i suoi riflessi sull'etica</i>
5	Raimondi, Francesco Paolo	<i>Per un lessico di Pietro Pomponazzi: il rapporto anima-corpo e i suoi riflessi sull'etica</i>
6	Spruit, Leen	<i>The Origin of the Soul from Antiquity to the Early Modern Era. A Short Introduction Lugano, Agorà, 2014</i>
7	Spruit, Leen	<i>The Controversy over the Animal Soul in Roman Censorship, Lugano, Agorà, 2015</i>
8	Taurino, Daniele	<i>Il "mind-body problem" a partire dalla questione animale una svolta etica dopo quella linguistica?</i>

Data sources

As mentioned above, the texts can be traced back to seven main archives:

- *BD*, corresponding to the section 'Database of philosophical texts of the modern age' (<https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/BD/>);
- *Daphnet*, corresponding to the section 'Daphnet – Digital Archives of PHilosophical texts on the NET' (<http://www.daphnet.iliesi.cnr.it/>);
- *ATSS*, corresponding to the section 'Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism' (https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/spinoza/home_spinoza.html);
- *DirVico*, corresponding to the digital resource 'Complete works of Giambattista Vico' (<https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/DirVico/Bookreader/html/app.html>);
- *AFR*, corresponding to the digital resource 'Archive of Renaissance philosophers' (<https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/afr/index.php>);
- *Fonti online*, corresponding to the digital resource 'Online Sources – Documentary support for ILIESI publications' (https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/fonti_online/);
- *Prin*, corresponding to the digital resource 'ILIESI Prin – The body-soul problem in the light of ethics' (<https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/prin/>).

Structure and formats

As with lexica, the structure and format of a text may vary depending on the archive it is referencing. For this reason, there is a separate section for each archive with the relevant details.

The philosophical texts belonging to the archive 'Database of philosophical texts of the modern age' include two basic components, which are listed below:

- a bibliographical schema with a link to the title page;
- a digital edition divided into two main sections:
 - Text, organised into documents that contain possible hypertext links to:
 - list of forms coded as proper noun,
 - list of forms coded as misprint,
 - list of forms coded as philosophical school,
 - list of forms coded as titles of work;
 - Lemmata.

The two components mentioned above are available in the following formats:

Component	Format	Sample
Bibliographical schema	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • text (html) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wolff
Digital edition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cod • text (html) • pdf 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wolff • pdf

Features of the COD file

This section shows an example of a search result for the lemma 'empiricus' found in the document 195001001 belonging to the philosophical text 'Psychologiae Empiricae' written by Cristian Wolff.

The first part shows the text, the second part (grey background) shows the lemmas related to the text above, with the occurrences of the search word 'empiricus' highlighted in bold.

1. 1 par. 1 Prol
— Psychologiae Empiricae | Prolegomena. | Par. 1. |
Psychologiae empiricae definitio.
| *P*(*Psychologia empirica* est scientia stabiliendi | principia per experientiam, unde ratio | redditur eorum, quae in anima humana | fiunt. | ~ Psychologiae empiricae definitionem jam | dedimus in Discursu praeliminari Logicae | praemisso (Par. 111.). Monuimus quoque | ibidem (*not.* Par. 112.), cura Psychologia rationali | eam distinguamus. Principia Psychologiae, | quae a posteriori stabiliuntur, maximam habent per universam | philosophiam practicam, immo per omnem quoque Theologiam | tam naturalem, quam revelatam, utilitatem. Quamobrem cum in | Psychologia rationali tradantur, quae, cum principiis nondum obvis | nitantur, in disputationem adducuntur; ea, quae veritatibus arduis | tanquam fundamentum substerni debent, ab illis separari conveniebat. | Sed de iis, quae jam alibi legi possunt, plura non dicimus.

empiricus[b].-a-um **empiricus**[b], "psychologia empirica" psychologia.-ae psychologia, "psychologia empirica"

Below is an extract from the same document in the COD file:

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296 0AA;TESTO INTEGRALE          LATINO          WOLFF
297          PSYCHOLOGIA EMPIRICA          195001001
298          P. 1 PAR. 1 PROL
299 0EE+ms Psychologiae Empiricae -ms [&] Prolegomena. [&] Par&. 1. [&]
300 +nm+cv Psychologiae empiricae definitio. -cv -nm [&] +cv
301 P{Sychologia -cv +cv empirica -cv est scientia stabiliendi [&]
302 principia per experientiam, unde ratio [&] redditur eorum, quae
303 in anima humana [&] fiunt. [&] ~ Psychologiae empiricae
304 definitionem jam [&] dedimus in Discursu praeliminari Logicae
305 [&] praemisso (Par&. 111.). Monuimus quoque [&] ibidem (+cv
306 not&. -cv Par&. 112.), cura Psychologia rationali [&] eam
307 distinguamus. Principia Psychologiae, [&] quae a posteriori
308 stabiliuntur, maximam habent per universam [&] philosophiam
309 practicam, immo per omnem quoque Theologiam [&] tam naturalem,
310 quam revelatam, utilitatem. Quamobrem cum in [&] Psychologia
311 rationali tradantur, quae, cum principiis nondum obviis [&]
312 nitantur, in disputationem adducuntur; ea, quae veritatibus
313 arduis [&] tanquam fundamentum substerni debent, ab illis
314 separari conveniebat. [&] Sed de iis, quae jam alibi legi
315 possunt, plura non dicimus. [&]
316 0FA (Wolff, PE, 1 par. 1 Prol).
317 0FF empiricus[b],-a-um empiricus[b],"psychologia empirica"
318 psychologia,-ae psychologia,"psychologia empirica"
319 ***SALT 0016413 000

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To better understand the structure and contents of a COD file, see *Appendix B*.

The texts belonging to the 'Modern Philosophy' section of the 'Daphnet – Digital Archives of Philosophical texts on the NET' archive include the following main components

- a biographical schema, in several languages;
- a bibliographical schema, in various languages, with possible editorial annotations (in text format) and title page (in image format);
- a digital edition divided into three main sections: metadata, pages, paragraphs (text, lemmata).

The various components mentioned above are available in the following formats:

Component	Format	Sample
Biographical schema	• text (html)	Baumgarten
Bibliographical schema	• text (html)	BauMPh
Digital edition	• xml tei • text (html, rdf)	baumph2.xml

The texts belonging to the 'Digital Library' section of the 'Daphnet – Digital Archives of Philosophical texts on the NET' archive include the following basic components:

- a bibliographical schema containing the main information about the work (author, title, date of publication and reference component);
- a digital edition that allows users to download the file (if it is in XML format) or to view it and then download it (if it is in HTML and PDF formats).

The different components mentioned above are available in the following formats:

Component	Format	Sample
Bibliographical schema	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • text (html) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDL/article/view/19
Digital edition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • xml • html • pdf 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDL/article/view/19/8 (xml) • DDL/article/view/374/304 (html) • DDL/article/view/625/466 (pdf)

The texts belonging to the 'Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism' include the following three basic components:

- a biographical schema, with possible links to documents related to the archive;
- a bibliographical schema;
- a digital edition.

The various components mentioned above are available in the following formats:

Component	Format	Sample
Biographical schema	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • text (html) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spinoza, Baruch (html)
Bibliographical schema	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • text (html) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cogitata metaphysica (html)
Digital edition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • html • jpg 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • cogitata_xhtml.html • SpiCMfron.jpg

The texts belonging to the 'Archive of Renaissance Philosophers' include the following three basic components

- a biographical schema, with possible links to documents related to the archive;
- one or more bibliographical schemas;
- a digital edition.

These three components are available in the following formats:

Component	Format	Sample
Biographical schema	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • text (html) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vanini, Giulio Cesare
Bibliographical schema	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • text (html) • gif 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dagmar von Wille, Schede bibliografiche (2017), scheda 3 • Virgilio Salvestrini, Bibliografia (1958), scheda 6
Digital edition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • jpg • gif • xml 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giordano Bruno, Cabala del cavallo pegaseo (1585) • Giulio Cesare Vanini, Amphitheatrum aeternae providentiae • Tommaso Campanella, Aforismi politici

The texts belonging to the 'Opere complete di Giambattista Vico' archive include two basic components, listed below:

- a bibliographical schema;
- a digital edition.

The two components mentioned above are available in the following formats:

Component	Format	Sample
Bibliographical schema	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> text (html) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Le Orazioni inaugurali, il De Itolorum sapientia e le Polemiche
Digital edition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> jpg text (html) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Le Orazioni inaugurali, il De Itolorum sapientia e le Polemiche Le Orazioni inaugurali, il De Itolorum sapientia e le Polemiche

Metadata

The metadata of a text can include a variety of information describing the content, structure and context of the text itself.

The main metadata identified for each archive can be divided into

- **Collection** (primary resource): a category that collects and organises a set of items with common characteristics (in this case, a text);
- **Biographical schema** (secondary resource): a document that gathers the main data and information about the author of a work in order to contextualise his activity;
- **Bibliographical schema** (secondary resource): a document containing the main data relating to a textual work, useful for identifying and describing it in a bibliographical context.

Number and size

Below is a summary table to collect, for each collection, information such as the number and size in terms of number of works, pages and size of the file(s) relating to the texts.

N.	Collection	Section	Number of works
1	Database of philosophical texts of the modern age	List of works in Latin	68
		List of works in English	21
		List of works in French	7
		List of works in Italian	31
2	Daphnet – Modern Philosophy*	Documentation	53
		Archive	109
3	Daphnet – Digital Library	Sources	109
4	Archive of Renaissance philosophers	(Giordano Bruno)	
		Texts	15
		Translations	6
		(Tommaso Campanella)	
		Italian texts	23
		Latin texts	40
5	Giambattista Vico's Complete Works	(G. C. Vanini)	
		Texts	2
5	Giambattista Vico's Complete Works	Texts	8

N.	Collection	Section	Number of works
6	Online Sources – Documentary support for ILIESI publications	Sources	10
7	ILIESI PRIN	Hypertext Publications	5 8
<i>Total</i>			457

1.1.1.3 LETTERS

The correspondence of philosophers is a valuable source of information, not only for understanding their philosophical ideas, but also for learning about the historical, social and personal context in which they operated. The letters of philosophers often reveal lesser-known aspects of their lives, including personal relationships, daily difficulties, and interactions with other intellectuals of the time. Through these correspondences we can observe the development of their thought and the way in which their ideas evolved in response to historical events, contemporary criticism and dialogue with colleagues. The ILIESI portal includes the ‘Archive of Renaissance Philosophers’ among the digital resources available for the study of correspondence.

The ‘**Archive of Renaissance Philosophers**’ brings together a vast collection of letters written by the most important thinkers of the time, offering privileged access to their lives and ideas. These correspondences, often exchanged with other intellectuals, patrons and influential figures of the time, provide direct evidence of the cultural, social and political dynamics of the Renaissance. The letters reveal not only the philosophical reflections of their authors, but also their personal experiences, intellectual debates, aspirations and difficulties. Through these letters we can better understand the historical context in which they operated, the network of relationships that supported their work, and the evolution of Renaissance thought.

Details of each section are given below.

Tommaso Campanella

In the 'Texts' section there is a subsection called 'Letters' which contains a series of letters written by Tommaso Campanella.

The letters

The letters offer an in-depth insight into Campanella's life and thought, revealing his relationships with other important figures of the time, his philosophical reflections and his personal and intellectual struggles. Through these letters it is possible to trace the evolution of his thought and to better understand the historical and cultural context in which he operated.

N.	Author	Title	Editor	Digital curator
1	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Lettere</i>	Ernst, Germana	Liburdi, Annarita

The letters can also be found in the ‘Documents’ section of the Archive, under the heading ‘Chronological Grouping’.

Chronological Grouping

The letters are organised in sections, each covering specific years. The collection contains 878 documentary collections. In relation to the documentary collections, this section includes a list of the editions associated with the letters. Each letter may have more than one reference edition.

Giulio Cesare Vanini

In the 'Documents' section, the documents are presented in chronological order, preceded by a progressive numbering that gives a summary title of the content, the date, topical-archival indications and any clarifying notes. Furthermore, each document is followed by its translation into Italian. There are 223 documents, mainly relating to Vanini's life, with particular attention to his correspondence.

Data sources

As mentioned above, the letters can be traced to a main archive:

- *AFR*, corresponding to the digital resource 'Archive of Renaissance philosophers' (<https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/afr/index.php>)

Structure and formats

The structure and format of a letter may vary depending on the reference section, but in general a letter includes several basic components, which are listed below:

- a bibliographical schema containing the main information about the work (author/sender, receiver, title, date, place of destination, place of origin, etc.)
- a digital edition (image or text)
- any hyperlinks to other resources, such as the bibliographical material contained in each record, which provide further information about the digital edition of the work.

The different components mentioned above are available in the following formats:

Component	Format	Sample
Bibliographical schema	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • text (html) 	ATC
Digital edition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • transcription (xml) • facsimile (jpg) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lettera n.1 (xml) • Lettera n.4 (jpg)
Hyperlinks	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • text (php/html) 	ATC/schede

Metadata

The metadata of a letter can include a variety of information describing the content, structure and context of the letter itself.

The main metadata identified can be divided into

- **Collection** (primary resource): a category that collects and organises a set of items with common characteristics (in this case, a letter);

- **Biographical schema** (secondary resource): a document that gathers the main data and information about the author of a letter in order to contextualise his activity;
- **Bibliographical schema** (secondary resource): a document containing the main data relating to a letter, useful for identifying and describing it in a bibliographical context.

Number and size

Below is a summary table to collect, for each collection, information such as the number and size in terms of number of works, pages and size of the file(s) relating to the letters.

N.	Collection	Section	Number of works
1	Archive of Renaissance philosophers	Texts (Tommaso Campanella)	878
		Documents (G. C. Vanini)	TBC*
<i>Total</i>			

* The exact number of letters contained in the Giulio Cesare Vanini Archive section is to be determined.

1.1.1.4 DOCUMENTS

The 'Document' resource type is described below in its current state, with emphasis on its peculiarities and distinctive features.

The history of philosophy is littered with documents and works in which philosophers write about other famous philosophers. These texts not only provide an in-depth understanding of the ideas and theories proposed, but often reveal personal aspects and anecdotes about the lives of the authors. Through books, essays and journal articles, some philosophers have allowed us to get to know thinkers such as Bruno, Campanella and Vanini better. These documents represent a timeless intellectual dialogue that continues to influence and enrich the modern philosophical landscape.

On the ILIESI portal, among the digital resources available for the study of documents, users can find the following sections:

- Daphnet – Digital Archives of Philosophical Texts on the NET,
- Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism,
- Archive of Renaissance philosophers,
- ILIESI PRIN,
- Illness in ConText: words of philosophy and guidance during the pandemic.

Daphnet – Digital Archives of Philosophical Texts on the NET

Daphnet, an acronym for 'Digital Archives of PHilosophical Texts on the NET', is a digital platform dedicated to the collection, preservation and dissemination of philosophical texts in digital format. Daphnet's main goal is to make philosophical texts of historical and scientific relevance available to a wide audience, thus facilitating research and study in the field of philosophy.

On the ILIESI portal, the section 'Daphnet – Digital Archives of Philosophical Texts on the NET' provides access to the 'Modern Philosophy' platform and the 'Daphnet Digital Library'.

The 'Daphnet Digital Library' is the platform of secondary sources offering a selection of critical contributions centred on the texts contained in the Daphnet portal. The contributions (mostly taken from the catalogue of printed volumes and ILIESI journals) are linked to the texts included in the Daphnet platforms and to the articles published in the international journal *Lexicon Philosophicum*.

The texts are included in a main section 'Sources', which contains a vast range of materials essential for the study of philosophy. In this section users will find the following categories:

- *Lexicon Philosophicum*;
- *ILIESI Colloquia*;
- *Elenchos*.

Lexicon Philosophicum

This section contains 'Lexicon Philosophicum', an academic journal devoted to philosophical topics and the history of philosophy. The collection comprises 5 volumes, all of which are available in this section. The journal publishes research articles, studies and discussions on various aspects of philosophy, contributing to the understanding and development of philosophical thought.

- ***Lexicon Philosophicum 1, 1985***: The contents of this specific edition include articles and essays by philosophers and scholars of the period, dealing with relevant and innovative topics in the field of philosophy.

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	Bianchi, Massimo Luigi	<i>Anima: la costruzione di una voce sperimentale nel lessico filosofico dei secoli XVII e XVIII</i>
2	Duro, Aldo	<i>Suità: storia di un termine apparentemente ignoto</i>
3	Lamarra, Antonio	<i>Leibniz e la περιχωρησις</i>

- ***Lexicon Philosophicum 2, 1987***: This volume contains research articles, essays and discussions on various aspects of philosophy, contributing to the understanding and development of philosophical thought.

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	Avalle, D'Arco Silvio	<i>Problemi di calcolo e lemmatizzazione</i>
2	Fourment Berni-Canani, Michele	<i>Anno/an-année (Projet pour une entrée de dictionnaire bilingue)</i>
3	Spinosa, Giacinta	<i>Un "thesaurus strutturato" per la gestione automatica del lemmario latino del lessico filosofico dei secoli XVII e XVIII</i>
4	Tognon, Giuseppe	<i>Leibniz e la costruzione degli essais de théodicée. Edizione e commento dell'indice autografo</i>

- ***Lexicon Philosophicum 3, 1988***: This volume contributes to the understanding and development of philosophy through the contributions of scholars and philosophers.

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	Procesi, Claudio	<i>Imagination and the building of mathematics</i>
2	Procesi, Lidia	<i>Il mito nel lessico giovanile schellinghiano</i>

3	Rath, Norbert	<i>"Natur in der Natur" Aspekte von Hölderlins Werkbegriff</i>
4	Rizzi, Lino	<i>Speculazione e superamento estetico in Schiller</i>
5	Tognon, Giuseppe	<i>L'immaginazione nella filosofia di Leibniz</i>
6	Totaro, Pina	<i>Perfectio e realitad nell'opera di Spinoza</i>

- **Lexicon Philosophicum 4, 1989:** This volume continues the journal's mission to contribute to the understanding and development of philosophy, including contributions from various scholars and philosophers.

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	Canone, Eugenio	<i>L'“Ermahnung an die Teutsche” di G. W. Leibniz. Index locorum</i>
2	Lamarra, Antonio	<i>Richard Rorty e la conoscenza come rappresentazione nota su un'interpretazione storiografica</i>
3	Palaia, Roberto	<i>Appunti sui concetti di natura e forza nell'epistolario fra Leibniz e Sturm</i>
4	Pimpinella, Pietro	<i>L'aesthetica di Baumgarten gnoseologia leibniziana e retorica antica</i>
5	Spinosa, Giacinta	<i>L'Aristotele latino nel thesaurus mediae et recentioris Latinitatis del lessico intellettuale europeo</i>
6	Tognon, Giuseppe	<i>Christian Wolff e gli “essais de théodicée” di Leibniz</i>
7	Veneziani, Marco	<i>Le “orazioni inaugurali” di Giambattista Vico concordanze e indici</i>

- **Lexicon Philosophicum 5, 1991:** This volume continues to contribute to the understanding and development of philosophy through the contributions of prominent scholars and philosophers.

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	Gregory, Tullio	<i>Sul lessico filosofico latino del Seicento e del Settecento</i>
2	Canone, Eugenio; Totaro, Pina	<i>Il “tractatus de intellectus emendatione” di Spinoza. Index locorum</i>
3	Di Bella, Stefano	<i>Il requisitum leibniziano come pars e ratio: tra inerenza e causalità</i>
4	Perilli, Lorenzo	<i>Il lessico intellettuale di Ippocrate σημαίνειν e τεκμαίρεσθαι</i>

ILIESI Colloquia

The volumes of the *Colloqui Internazionali ILIESI*, published by the prestigious Olschki, can be found in this section.

Each volume is dedicated to the in-depth study of a single term of significant philosophical importance, and is therefore an invaluable resource for scholars and philosophy enthusiasts. The collection currently includes the following volumes:

- ***I Colloquio Internazionale, Roma, 7-9 gennaio 1974. A cura di M. Fattori e M. Bianchi, 1976***: This volume collects the proceedings of the first International Colloquium, which was held in Rome from 7 to 9 January 1974. Published in 1976, this inaugural event kicked off the series of meetings and publications exploring terms of great philosophical relevance, marking the beginning of a high-level academic tradition.

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	Garin, Eugenio	<i>Relazione introduttiva</i>
2	Gregory, Tullio	<i>Rapport sur les activités du "lessico intellettuale europeo"</i>
3	Delatte, Louis	<i>Analyse thématique automatique</i>
4	Robinet, André	<i>La specificité du langage philosophique au XVIIe siècle</i>
5	Autori Vari	<i>Discussione</i>
6	Heintel, Erich	<i>Relazione</i>
7	Vercruysse, Jeroom	<i>Le "Vrijdenkerslexicon" de Bruxelles</i>
8	Hall, Roland	<i>A philosopher's contribution to philosophical lexicography</i>
9	Costabel, Pierre; Armogathe, Jean-Robert	<i>Premiers résultats de l'"Équipe Descartes"</i>
10	Ottonello, Pietro Paolo	<i>Problemi e struttura del "Lessico Rosminiano"</i>
11	Quemada, Bernard	<i>Quelques problèmes et solutions méthodologiques</i>
12	Robinet, André	<i>Premiers pas dans l'application de l'informatique à l'étude des textes philosophiques</i>
13	de Tollenaere, Felicien	<i>L'"Institut de Lexicologie Néerlandaise"</i>
14	Tombeur, Paul; Hamesse, Jacqueline	<i>Recherches en cours au "Centre de Traitement Électronique des Documents" (CETEDOC)</i>
15	Wenin, Christian	<i>Indexation de revues et lexiques philosophiques</i>

16	Diemer, Alwin	<i>Relazione</i>
17	Zampolli, Antonio	<i>Les dépouillements électroniques: quelques problèmes de méthode et d'organisation</i>
18	Duro, Aldo	<i>Rapport sur les réponses au questionnaire</i>
19	Autori Vari	<i>Discussione</i>
20	Autori Vari	<i>Dibattito generale</i>
21	Autori Vari	<i>Appendice I: Questionario</i>
22	Autori Vari	<i>Appendice II: Specimen del "Lessico di G. Bruno"</i>
23	Autori Vari	<i>Appendice III: Specimen del "Glossarium Epicureum"</i>

- **ORDO. Il Colloquio Internazionale, Roma, 7-9 gennaio 1977. A cura di M. Fattori e M. Bianchi, 1979:** This volume contains the proceedings of the Second International Colloquium held in Rome from 7 to 9 January 1977. The volume, published in 1979, is devoted to the term 'ordo', exploring its various philosophical facets, from scholastic interpretations to modern reflections. This meeting continued the tradition of in-depth study and debate on key concepts of philosophical thought that had begun with the first colloquium.

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	Équipe Descartes (C.N.R.S.)	<i>Contribution à la sémantèse d'ordre-ordo chez Descartes</i>
2	Becco, Anne	<i>Le terme ordre à travers deux textes de Leibniz discours de métaphysique et monadologie</i>
3	Autori Vari	<i>Dibattito</i>
4	Gregory, Tullio	<i>Pour un thesaurus mediae et recentioris latinitatis</i>
5	Duro, Aldo	<i>Pour un Thesaurus mediae et recentioris latinitatis. Aspects techniques</i>
6	Avalle, D'Arco Silvio	<i>Il Lessico italiano delle origini e l'informatica linguistica</i>
7	Bartoletti Colombo, Anna Maria	<i>Relazione sull'attività del Vocabolario giuridico italiano durante il triennio 1974-77</i>
8	Busa, Roberto SJ	<i>Activités depuis janvier 1974</i>
9	Delatte, Louis; Govaerts, Suzanne; Denooz, Joseph	<i>Note sur les activités du Laboratoire d'analyse statistique des langues anciennes</i>
10	Flury, Peter	<i>Der Thesaurus linguae latinae</i>

11	Gorcy, Gerard	<i>Rapport d'activité du Centre de recherche pour un Trésor de la langue française (1974- 1976)</i>
12	Gregory, Tullio	<i>Lessico intellettuale europeo (1974-1976)</i>
13	Hamesse, Jacqueline	<i>Les travaux de lexicographie philosophique médiévale menés de 1974 à 1977</i>
14	Oeing-Hanhoff, Ludger	<i>"Historisches Wörterbuch der Philosophie"</i>
15	Ricken, Ulrich	<i>Quelques activités lexicographiques dans les pays de l'Europe socialiste</i>
16	Tombeur, Paul	<i>Centre de traitement électronique des documents (CETEDOC). Recherches en cours</i>
17	Wenin, Christian	<i>Réalizations et projets de travaux informatiques à l'Institut supérieur de Philosophie (de langue française) de l'Université catholique de Louvain</i>
18	Zampolli, Antonio	<i>Division linguistique du CNUCE. Activités de 1974 à 1976</i>

- **RES. III Colloquio Internazionale, Roma, 7-9 gennaio 1980. A cura di M. Fattori e M. Bianchi, 1982:** This volume contains the proceedings of the 3rd International Colloquium held in Rome from 7 to 9 January 1980. The volume, published in 1982, is devoted to the term 'res'. It explores the various philosophical dimensions of the concept of 'res', analysing its meaning and use in different philosophical traditions.

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	Garin, Eugenio	<i>Relazione introduttiva</i>
2	Guilbaud, Georges Théodule	<i>Statistique et philologie</i>
3	Berni Canani, Ugo	<i>Graphes de relations sémantiques</i>
4	Flury, Peter	<i>Res im antiken latein</i>
5	Bartoletti Colombo, Anna Maria	<i>Usi e valori di res nelle novellae giustinianee</i>
6	Bautier, Anne-Marie	<i>Sens matériels de res et leurs correspondants en latin médiéval</i>
7	Hamesse, Jacqueline	<i>Res chez les auteurs philosophiques des 12 et 13 siècles</i>
8	Latham, Ronald	<i>Res/causa dans le fichier du lexique latin médiéval tiré de sources britanniques</i>
9	Gregory, Tullio	<i>Relazione sulle attività del lessico intellettuale europeo (1977-1979)</i>

- **SPIRITUS. IV Colloquio Internazionale, Roma, 7-9 gennaio 1983. A cura di M. Fattori e M. Bianchi, 1984:** This volume collects the proceedings of the 4th International Colloquium, held in Rome from 7 to 9 January 1983. Published in 1984, the volume is devoted to the term 'spiritus'. It analyses the different interpretations and philosophical implications of the concept of 'spirit', continuing the tradition of in-depth exploration of key terms in philosophical thought.

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	Garin, Eugenio	<i>Relazione introduttiva</i>
2	Petöfi, János S.	<i>Some aspects of the structure of a lexicon entry</i>
3	Delatte, Louis; Govaerts, Suzanne; Denooz, Joseph	<i>Note sur spiritus</i>
4	Flury, Peter	<i>Beobachtungen zum Gebrauch von spiritus im antiken Latein</i>
5	Sevrin, Jean-Marie	<i>Spiritus dans les versions latines de la bible</i>
6	Filoramo, Giovanni	<i>Spiritus e derivati nella tradizione eresilogica di lingua latina sullo gnosticismo</i>
7	Bautier, Anne-Marie	<i>Spiritus dans les textes antérieurs a 1200. Itinéraire lexicographique médiolatin: du souffle vital a l'au dela maléfique</i>
8	Latham, Ronald	<i>Spiritus dans le fichier du Lexique latin médiéval britannique</i>
9	Weijers, Olga	<i>Spiritus et ses dérivés dans le latin médiéval néerlandais</i>
10	Lamarra, Antonio	<i>Esprit nei nouveaux essais sur l'entendement humain di G. W. Leibniz</i>
11	Schepers, Heinrich	<i>Spiritus bei Leibnitz</i>
12	Ricken, Ulrich	<i>Un champ lexical et ses implications philosophiques a l'âge classique: l'abstrait et le concret dans les significations de spiritus, esprit et quelques dérivés</i>
13	Hall, Roland	<i>The concept of spirit in Locke's essay</i>
14	Pimpinella, Pietro	<i>Spiritus nella psychologia rationalis di Christian Wolff</i>
15	Hamesse, Jacqueline	<i>Spiritus chez les auteurs philosophiques des 12e et 13e siècles</i>
16	Busa, Roberto SJ	<i>De voce spiritus in operibus s. Thomae Aquinatis</i>
17	Walker, Daniel Pickering	<i>Medical Spirits and God and the Soul</i>

18	Debus, Allen George	<i>Chemistry and the Quest for a Material Spirit of Life in the Seventeenth Century</i>
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- **IDEA. VI Colloquio Internazionale, Roma, 5-7 gennaio 1989. A cura di M. Fattori e M. Bianchi, 1990:** This volume contains the proceedings of the 6th International Colloquium, held in Rome from 5 to 7 January 1989. The volume, published in 1990, is dedicated to the term 'idea'. It explores the genesis, development and impact of ideas in philosophical thought, offering contributions that analyse the concept from different historical and theoretical perspectives.

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	Saffrey, Henry-Dominique	<i>Origine, usage et signification du mot 'IDEA</i>
2	Pépin, Jean	<i>'IDEA/idea dans la patristique grecque et latine</i>
3	Spinosa, Giacinta	<i>Idea e Idos nella tradizione latina medievale</i>
4	de Rijk, Lambertus Marie	<i>Un tournant important dans l'usage du mot idea chez Henri de Gand</i>
5	Hamesse, Jacqueline	<i>Idea chez les auteurs philosophiques des 12 et 13 siècles</i>
6	Costabel, Pierre	<i>Idée et finction: sondages dans la mathématique de l'art analytique</i>
7	Armogathe, Jean-Robert	<i>Sémantèse d'idée/idea chez Descartes</i>
8	Robinet, André	<i>Idée dans les œuvres complètes de Malebranche</i>
9	Poser, Hans	<i>Der Begriff der Idee bei Leibniz</i>
10	Yolton, John William	<i>The term idea in the Seventeenth and Eighteenth-century British philosophy</i>
11	Hall, Roland	<i>Idea in Locke's works</i>
12	Mugnai, Paolo Francesco	<i>Idea nelle opere di Berkeley</i>
13	Costa, Gustavo	<i>Idea nella cultura italiana del Settecento: la posizione di Vico</i>
14	Ricken, Ulrich	<i>Idée / idee dans la pensée philosophique del lumières en France et en Allemagne</i>
15	Hinske, Norbert	<i>Kants Anverwandlung des Ursprünglichen Sinnes von Idee</i>
16	Moiso, Francesco	<i>Idee in Schelling</i>
17	Verra, Valerio	<i>Idee nel sistema hegeliano</i>
18	Gombrich, Ernst Hans Josef	<i>Idea in the theory of art: philosophy or rhetoric?</i>

- **EXPERIENTIA. X Colloquio Internazionale, Roma, 4-6 gennaio 2001. A cura di M. Fattori e M. Bianchi, 2002:** This volume collects the proceedings of the 10th International Colloquium, held in Rome from 4 to 6 January 2001. Published in 2002, this volume is dedicated to the term 'experientia'. It examines the concept of 'experience' from different philosophical perspectives, including epistemological, ontological and practical issues, thus continuing the tradition of critical and analytical study of key terms in philosophy promoted by the ILIESI International Colloquia.

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	Belardi, Walter	<i>Il costruirsi del campo lessicale nell'experientia in greco e latino</i>
2	Pépin, Jean	<i>Experimentum mali. Saint Augustin sur la connaissance du mal</i>
3	Hamesse, Jacqueline	<i>Experientia/experimentum dan les lexiques médiévaux et dans les textes philosophiques antérieurs au 4E siècle</i>
4	Leonardi, Claudio	<i>L'esperienza del divino in Francesco D'Assisi</i>
5	Busa, Roberto SJ	<i>Experientia, experimentalis, experimentum, experior, inexperientia, inexpers nell'aquinate e negli altri autori censiti nell'Index Thomisticus</i>
6	Spinosa, Giacinta	<i>Empeiria/experientia: modelli di 'prova' tra antichità, medioevo ed età cartesiana</i>
7	Bianchi, Massimo Luigi	<i>Il tema dell'esperienza in Paracelso</i>
8	Stabile, Giorgio	<i>Il concetto di esperienza in Galilei e nella scuola galileiana</i>
9	Fattori, Marta	<i>Experientia-experimentum: un confronto tra il corpus latino e inglese di Francis Bacon</i>
10	Armogathe, Jean-Robert	<i>Sémantèse d'experientia / experimentum / expériences dans le corpus cartésien</i>
11	Robinet, André	<i>Expérience dans l'oeuvre de Malebranche</i>
12	Totaro, Pina	<i>Experientia nella filosofia di Spinoza</i>

Elenchos

This section contains two specific issues of the academic journal *Elenchos*: one from 1986 and one from 1992.

- ***Elenchos, Anno XIII – 1992, Fasc. 1-2***

N.	Creator/Author	Title
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1	Sedley, David	<i>Sextus Empiricus and the atomist criteria of truth</i>
2	Classen, Carl Joachim	<i>L'esposizione dei sofisti e della sofistica in Senso Empirico</i>
3	Döring, Klaus	<i>DIE SOG. KLEINEN SOKRATIKER UND IHRE SCHULEN BEI SEXTUS EMPIRICUS</i>
4	Isnardi Parente, Margherita	<i>Sesto, Platone, l'accademia antica e i pitagorici</i>
5	Ioppolo, Anna Maria	<i>Sesto Empirico e l'accademia scettica</i>
6	Annas, Julia	<i>Sextus Empiricus and the peripatetics</i>
7	Hülser, Karlheinz	<i>Sextus Empiricus und Die Stoiker</i>
8	Decleva Caizzi, Fernanda	<i>Sesto e gli scettici</i>

- **Elenchos, Anno VII – 1986, Fasc. 1-2**

N.	Creatore/Autore	Titolo
1	Verbeke, Gerard	<i>Panétius et Posidonius chez Diogène Laërce</i>
2	Gigante, Marcello	<i>Biografia e dossografia in Diogene Laerzio</i>
3	Gigon, Olof	<i>DAS DRITTE BUCH DES DIOGENES LAERTIOS</i>
4	Giannantoni, Gabriele	<i>Socrate e i socratici in Diogene Laerzio</i>
5	Mansfeld, Jaap	<i>Diogenes Laertius on stoic philosophy</i>
6	Kindstrand, Jan Fredrik	<i>Diogenes Laertius and the chreia traditions</i>
7	Moraux, Paul	<i>Diogène Laërce et le peripatos</i>
8	Barnes, Jonathan	<i>Diogene Laerzio e il pirronismo</i>
9	Long, Anthony A.	<i>Diogenes Laertius, life of Arcesilaus</i>

Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism

The 'Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism' is a digital platform that collects multilingual philosophical texts by various authors, images and documentary material, with the aim of providing a tool for reading and deepening knowledge of the philosophy and influence of Baruch Spinoza, one of the great rationalists of the 17th century.

The images can be found in the main section 'Images'.

The 'Images' section offers a rich and varied collection of iconographic material relating to Spinoza. Here users can find images of the author, graphic representations and title pages of the various works preserved in the Archive. The section is divided into 3 other subsections:

- *Spinozan iconography* – The section currently consists of 25 images listed below:

N.	Creator/Author	Title
1	Georg Wienbrack	<i>Busto di Spinoza</i>
2	Pieter de Fode	<i>Ritratto di Masaniello (erroneamente attribuito a Spinoza, il quale si sarebbe ritratto nelle vesti di Masaniello)</i>
3	-	<i>Ritratto di giovane (erroneamente ritenuto il ritratto di Spinoza)</i>
4	-	<i>Ritratto conservato nella Herzog August Bibliothek Wolfenbüttel</i>
5	-	<i>Copia del ritratto conservato nella Herzog August Bibliothek Wolfenbüttel</i>
6	-	<i>Incisione stampata di Spinoza (Opera Posthuma)</i>
7	Hendrik van der Spyck	<i>Ritratto di Spinoza</i>
8	Wallerant Vaillant	<i>Ritratto di Spinoza</i>
9	Foost van Craesbeeck	<i>Ritratto di Spinoza</i>
10	-	<i>Uomo con il cappello. Erroneamente ritenuto il ritratto di Spinoza</i>
11	Mark Antokolski	<i>Statua di Spinoza</i>
12	Félix Mendes da Costa	<i>Statua di Spinoza</i>
13	Karl Bayer	<i>Ritratto di Spinoza</i>
14	P. F. Arenzen	<i>Spinoza</i>
15	H. Lips	<i>Spinoza</i>
16	-	<i>Spinoza</i>
17	Willem Goeree	<i>Spinoza</i>
18	Fr. Roth-Scholtz	<i>Spinoza (Icones)</i>
19	Christian Wolf	<i>Spinoza (B. v. S. Sittenlebre)</i>
20	-	<i>Spinoza</i>
21	François	<i>Ritratto di Spinoza</i>
22	Ét. Fessard	<i>Spinoza</i>
23	Hendrik Lips	<i>Spinoza</i>

24	V. Froer	<i>Spinoza</i>
25	Wallerant Vaillant	<i>Spinoza, in The Jewish Encyclopedia</i>

Spinoza, ritratto di Hendrik van der Spuyck

Spinoza, statua in marmo di Mark Antokolski

Abravanel, Isaac ben Judah

Ambrogio Calepio

- *Various iconographies* – This section currently contains 76 illustrations of various types;
- *Title pages* – This section currently contains 42 title pages of the works that are present in the Archive.

Diophantus Alexandrinus,
Arithmeticon libri sex

Iohann Scapula
Lexicon Graeco-Latinum

Archive of Renaissance Philosophers

The Archive of Renaissance Philosophers preserves a rich collection of documents written by the most illustrious thinkers of the period, offering privileged access to their lives and ideas. These texts, often written for other intellectuals, patrons and prominent figures of the time, provide direct evidence of the cultural, social and political dynamics of the Renaissance. The documents reveal not only the philosophical reflections of their authors, but also their personal experiences, intellectual debates, aspirations and difficulties. Through these writings, we can better understand the historical context in which they operated, the network of relationships that supported their work, and the evolution of Renaissance thought.

Giordano Bruno

The **'Biography'** section provides details on the life of Giordano Bruno, based on the work *Giordano Bruno. Gli anni napoletani e la "peregrinatio" europea* (Giordano Bruno. The Neapolitan years and the European wandering), published in 1992 and edited by Eugenio Canone. Bruno (1548-1600) was an Italian pantheist philosopher, poet, cosmological theorist, and mnemonicist, who was tried for heresy by the Roman Inquisition and burned at the stake in Rome's Campo de' Fiori. The biographical archive is a collective work edited by various scholars and researchers (E. Canone, C. Carella, G. Ernst, A. Perfetti and others) who have contributed essays and studies on the life and works of Giordano Bruno during his years in Naples and his period of travelling in Europe. The information on Bruno's biography is divided into two different subsections:

- *Hypertext chronology* – There are currently no resources in this section;

- *Biographical contributions* – The section currently consists of 14 contributions, listed below:

N.	Author	Title	Digital curator
1	Canone, Eugenio	<i>1565-1566: Bruno entra nell'Ordine domenicano</i>	Canone, Eugenio
2	Canone, Eugenio	<i>La vita nel convento</i>	Canone, Eugenio
3	Canone, Eugenio	<i>Bruno 'studente formale' di teologia</i>	Canone, Eugenio
4	Canone, Eugenio	<i>Il primo incidente disciplinare durante il noviziato</i>	Canone, Eugenio
5	Canone, Eugenio	<i>Le vicende del processo napoletano del 1576</i>	Canone, Eugenio
6	Carella, Candida	<i>Le lezioni sulla Sphaera e il primo soggiorno a Venezia</i>	Canone, Eugenio
7	Ernst, Germana	<i>Bruno e l'opuscolo De' segni de' tempi</i>	Canone, Eugenio
8	Canone, Eugenio	<i>Bruno a Ginevra</i>	Canone, Eugenio
9	Carella, Candida	<i>Bruno e l'esemplare del Quod nihil scitur di Francisco Sanchez</i>	Canone, Eugenio
10	Canone, Eugenio	<i>Il primo soggiorno a Parigi</i>	Canone, Eugenio
11	Canone, Eugenio	<i>Bruno in Inghilterra</i>	Canone, Eugenio
12	Perfetti, Amalia	<i>Un nuovo documento sul secondo soggiorno parigino di Giordano Bruno (1585-1586)</i>	Canone, Eugenio
13	Canone, Eugenio	<i>"Hic ergo sapientia aedificavit sibi domum": il soggiorno di Bruno in Germania (1586-1591)</i>	Canone, Eugenio
14	Canone, Eugenio	<i>La prima lettera di denuncia di Giovanni Mocenigo all'inquisitore veneto</i>	Canone, Eugenio

The '**Documents**' section is divided into three main sub-sections:

- *Document Collections* – There are currently no resources in this section;
- *Chronological grouping* – There are currently no resources in this section;
- *Thematic grouping* – There are currently no resources in this section.

The '**Images**' section is divided into four sub-sections:

- *The Iconography of Giordano Bruno* – There are currently no resources in this section;
- *The Places* – There are currently no resources in this section;
- *The Texts* – There are currently no resources in this section;
- *The People* – There are currently no resources in this section.

The '**Bibliography**' section is divided into two sub-sections:

- *Historical and bibliographical records on Bruno's writings* – There are currently no resources in this section;

- *Historical and bibliographical records on Bruno's fortune* – There are currently no resources in this section.

The **'Studies and Materials'** section contains numerous documents relating to Giordano Bruno, a philosopher of great historical importance. This collection of texts and works provides an in-depth analysis of Bruno's life and ideas, examining not only his philosophical reflections but also his relationships with other intellectuals and prominent figures of his time. Thanks to these sources, it is possible to gain a detailed insight into his personal and intellectual struggles and to understand the impact of his theories and positions on the cultural and social context of the period. Each document sheds light on different aspects of his life and writings, allowing a deeper understanding of his contribution to the philosophy and culture of his time.

- *Studies* – The collection currently consists of 3 studies, listed below:

N.	Author	Title	Digital curator
1	Canone, Eugenio	<i>Mosaico bruniano: immagini e parole</i>	Canone, Eugenio
2	Bruno, Giordano	<i>Voci dell'Enciclopedia bruniana</i>	Canone, Eugenio
3	Canone, Eugenio	<i>Giordano Bruno. Gli anni napoletani e la "peregrinatio" europea: Immagini – Testi – Documenti</i>	Canone, Eugenio

- *Materials* – The collection currently consists of 2 materials, listed below:

N.	Author	Title	Digital curator
1	Liburdi, Annarita	<i>Concordanze di pagine delle edizioni moderne e delle traduzioni de La cena de le Ceneri di Giordano Bruno</i>	Canone, Eugenio
2	De Lagarde, Paul	<i>[Indice dei nomi e delle cose notabili] e [Relazione sui criteri della propria edizione]</i>	Canone, Eugenio

The **'B&C'** section – dedicated to the **Enciclopedia Bruniana e Campanelliana** – and the **'Bulletin board'** section currently contain no resources.

Tommaso Campanella

The **'Documents'** section contains various types of documents, including journal articles, essays and books, relating to Tommaso Campanella, an Italian philosopher, theologian and poet of the late Renaissance (1568-1639) who was prosecuted by the Roman Inquisition for heresy in 1594 and spent years in prison. These materials provide an in-depth insight into Campanella's life and thought, revealing his relationships with other important figures of the time, his philosophical reflections, and his personal and intellectual struggles. The section is divided into three main sections:

- *Documentary collections* – The collection currently consists of 9 documents, listed below:

N.	Author	Title	Editor	Digital curator
1	Capiabbi, Vito	<i>Documenti inediti circa la voluta ribellione di F. Tommaso Campanella</i>	-	Canone, Eugenio
2	Amabile, Luigi	<i>Fra Tommaso Campanella, la sua congiura, i suoi processi e la sua pazzia, t. III</i>	-	Liburdi, Annarita
3	Amabile, Luigi	<i>Fra Tommaso Campanella ne' castelli di Napoli, in Roma ed in Parigi, t. II, sez. Documenti</i>	-	Liburdi, Annarita
4	Firpo, Luigi	<i>I primi processi campanelliani in una ricostruzione unitaria see in "Giornale critico della filosofia italiana", XX, 1939, pp. 5-43. Ristampato in Luigi Firpo, I processi di Tommaso Campanella, a cura di Eugenio Canone, Roma, Salerno Editrice, 1998, pp. 5-43 (journal)</i>	-	Canone, Eugenio
5	Firpo, Luigi	<i>La congiura di Calabria. Narrazioni, documenti, verbali delle torture</i>	-	Canone, Eugenio
6	Firpo, Luigi	<i>I processi di Tommaso Campanella</i>	-	Canone, Eugenio
7	Spruit, Leen	<i>I processi campanelliani tra Padova e Calabria: documenti inediti dall'archivio dell'Inquisizione Romana see in Germana Ernst (a cura di), Tommaso Campanella e la congiura di Calabria. Atti del convegno di Stilo (18-19 novembre 1999) in occasione del IV centenario della congiura, ed. Comune di Stilo, Stilo, 2001, pp. 237-241 (book)</i>	-	Canone, Eugenio
8	Moro, Giacomo	<i>Documenti veneti su Campanella e sul processo per la fallita evasione see in "Bruniana & Campanelliana", XV, 2, 2009, pp. 463-487 (journal)</i>	-	Canone, Eugenio
9	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Lettere</i>	Ernst, G.	Liburdi, Annarita

- *Chronological grouping* – Within this section, we can also find traces of letters, which are organised chronologically. Each section covers specific years, divided into 878 documentary collections;
- *Thematic grouping* – There are currently no resources in this section.

The **'Images'** section of the archive contains a valuable visual heritage that offers an in-depth look at Campanella's life and work. This archive includes photographs and illustrations of the places where the philosopher lived and wrote, capturing the essence of the environments that inspired his intellectual production. It also includes the letters he exchanged during his lifetime, revealing the dynamics of his personal and professional relationships. The collection is completed by the texts that marked his work, offering a journey through Campanella's literary and philosophical legacy.

This section is divided into five sub-sections

- *The Iconography of Tommaso Campanella* – There are currently no resources in this section;
- *The Places* – The collection currently consists of 7 places, listed below:

N.	Author	Title of the work main ed.	Title of the work
1	Pacichelli, Giovan Battista	<i>Il Regno di Napoli in prospettiva diviso in dodeci provincie</i> , Napoli, Michele Luigi Mutio, vol. II.	<i>Calabria Ulteriore</i>
2	Pacichelli, Giovan Battista	<i>Il Regno di Napoli in prospettiva diviso in dodeci provincie</i> , Napoli, Michele Luigi Mutio, vol. II.	<i>Stilo</i>
3	Pacichelli, Giovan Battista	<i>Il Regno di Napoli in prospettiva diviso in dodeci provincie</i> , Napoli, Michele Luigi Mutio, vol. II.	<i>San Giorgio Morgeto</i>
4	Pacichelli, Giovan Battista	<i>Il Regno di Napoli in prospettiva diviso in dodeci provincie</i> , Napoli, Michele Luigi Mutio, vol. II.	<i>Nicastro (Lamezia)</i>
5	Pacichelli, Giovan Battista	<i>Il Regno di Napoli in prospettiva diviso in dodeci provincie</i> , Napoli, Michele Luigi Mutio, vol. II.	<i>Cosenza</i>
6	Pacichelli, Giovan Battista	<i>Il Regno di Napoli in prospettiva diviso in dodeci provincie</i> , Napoli, Michele Luigi Mutio, vol. II.	<i>Napoli</i>
7	Pacichelli, Giovan Battista	<i>Il Regno di Napoli in prospettiva diviso in dodeci provincie</i> , Napoli, Michele Luigi Mutio, vol. II.	<i>Castelvetere (Caulonia)</i>

Calabria Ulteriore. Incisione ad acquaforte, tratta da Giovan Battista Pacichelli, *Il Regno di Napoli in prospettiva diviso in dodici provincie*, Napoli, Michele Luigi Mutio, 1703, vol. II. Roma, Biblioteca del Senato della Repubblica.

- *The Texts* – - The collection currently consists of 18 title pages, listed below:

N.	Author	Title of the reference work
1	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Apologia pro Galileo</i>
2	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Astrologia libri VI</i>
3	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Astrologia libri VII</i>
4	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Atheismus triumphatus</i>
5	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Atheismus triumphatus</i>
6	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>De gentilismo non retinendo</i>
7	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Medicina</i>
8	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Metaphysica</i>
9	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Philosophia rationalis</i>
10	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Philosophia realis</i>
11	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Philosophia realis epilogistica</i>
12	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Philosophia sensibus demonstrata</i>
13	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>De praedestinatione</i>
14	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Prodromus philosophiae instaurandae</i>
15	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>De sensu rerum et magia</i>
16	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>De sensu rerum et magia</i>
17	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Syntagma de libris propriis</i>
18	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Scelta d'alcune poesie filosofiche</i>

- *The People* – There are currently no resources in this section;
- *The Letters* – This section contains the letters written by Tommaso Campanella and addressed to *Al Cavalier Cassiano Dal Pozzo in Roma e ad Ascanio Filomarino (?) in Roma* (to the Cavalier Cassiano Dal Pozzo in Rome and to Ascanio Filomarino (?) in Rome). The letters are dated in the following years: 1624, 1635 and 1638. The collection currently consists of 9 letters, listed below:

N.	Author	Title of the reference work
1	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Al Cavalier Cassiano Dal Pozzo in Roma, Napoli, 25 giugno 1624</i>
2	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Al Cavalier Cassiano Dal Pozzo in Roma, Napoli, 20 luglio 1624</i>
3	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Al Cavalier Cassiano Dal Pozzo in Roma, Napoli, 10 agosto 1624</i>
4	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Ad Ascanio Filomarino (?) in Roma, Napoli, 13 agosto 1624</i>
5	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Al Cavalier Cassiano Dal Pozzo in Roma, Napoli, 18 novembre 1624</i>
6	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Al Cavalier Cassiano Dal Pozzo in Roma, Parigi, 14 marzo 1635</i>
7	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Al Cavalier Cassiano Dal Pozzo in Roma, Parigi, 4 giugno 1635</i>
8	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Al Cavalier Cassiano Dal Pozzo in Roma, Parigi, 9 ottobre 1635</i>
9	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Al Cavalier Cassiano Dal Pozzo in Roma, Parigi, 27 luglio 1638</i>

The '**Bibliography**' section contains a series of documents written by various authors and dedicated to the life and works of the philosopher. This collection of texts provides an in-depth and detailed overview of Campanella's life, works and philosophy. The documentation provides an enriched and contextualised explanation of Campanella's thought, helping to better understand his ideas and their historical and cultural impact. The section is divided into two sub-sections:

- *Historical and bibliographical records on Campanella's writings* – The collection currently consists of 5 records listed below:

N.	Author	Title	Digital Edition
1	Firpo, Luigi	<i>Bibliografia degli scritti di Tommaso Campanella</i>	Canone, Eugenio
2	Ernst, Germana	<i>Le antiche stampe di Tommaso Campanella. Schede dei manoscritti</i>	Canone, Eugenio
3	Guerrini, Luigi	<i>Schede delle antiche stampe campanelliane e della biografia di Cyprianus</i>	Canone, Eugenio
4	Suggi, Andrea	<i>Schede storico-bibliografiche redatte per i testi-base del Lessico etico-religioso e politico di Tommaso Campanella</i>	Canone, Eugenio

N.	Author	Title	Digital Edition
5	Sistema Bibliotecario Vibonese	<i>Edizioni campanelliane originali nelle biblioteche calabresi</i>	Canone, Eugenio

- *Historical and bibliographical records on Campanella's fortune* – There are currently no resources in this section.

The **'Studies and Materials'** section contains numerous documents on Tommaso Campanella, a philosopher of great historical importance. This collection of texts and works offers a detailed analysis of Campanella's life and ideas, exploring not only his philosophical reflections, but also his interactions with other intellectuals and prominent figures of his time. These sources allow a full understanding of his personal and intellectual challenges, and show how his ideas influenced the culture and society of his time. Each document sheds light on different aspects of his life and works, helping to better understand his impact on the philosophy and culture of his time. There is also a sub-section with indexes of the main texts by Tommaso Campanella and Luigi Amabile.

- *Studies* – The collection currently consists of 19 studies, listed below:

N.	Author	Title	Digital curator
1	Plastina, Sandra	<i>Galleria dell'Accademia Cosentina. Parte seconda</i>	Canone, Eugenio
2	Sergio, Emilio	<i>Galleria dell'Accademia Cosentina. Parte prima</i>	Canone, Eugenio
3	Giovanozzi, Delfina	<i>"Liberò, ma cattolico pensatore". Tommaso Campanella nei manuali italiani di storia della filosofia del XIX secolo</i>	Canone, Eugenio
4	Moro, Giacomo	<i>Documenti veneti su Campanella e sul processo per la fallita evasione</i>	Canone, Eugenio
5	Canone, Eugenio	<i>Il volto di Tommaso Campanella. Dipinti e incisioni</i>	Canone, Eugenio
6	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Voci dell'Enciclopedia campanelliana</i>	Canone, Eugenio
7	Ernst, Germana	<i>Postilla sull'abiura di Campanella e sul rogo dell'inglese</i>	Canone, Eugenio
8	Spruit, Leen	<i>A proposito dell'abiura di Campanella nel 1595</i>	Canone, Eugenio
9	Longo, Carlo	<i>Su gli anni giovanili di fr. Tommaso Campanella O.P. (1568-1589)</i>	Canone, Eugenio
10	De Vinci, Antonella	<i>Fra le letture del giovane Tommaso Campanella</i>	Canone, Eugenio
11	Spruit, Leen	<i>I processi campanelliani tra Padova e Calabria: documenti inediti dall'archivio dell'Inquisizione Romana</i>	Canone, Eugenio
12	Baldini, Enzo A.	<i>Luigi Firpo e Campanella: cinquant'anni di ricerche e di pubblicazioni</i>	Canone, Eugenio
13	Firpo, Luigi	<i>I processi di Tommaso Campanella (1998), a cura di Eugenio Canone</i>	Canone, Eugenio

N.	Author	Title	Digital curator
14	Ernst, Germana	<i>Introduzione</i>	Canone, Eugenio
15	Ernst, Germana	<i>Campanella e il De tribus impostoribus</i>	Canone, Eugenio
16	Firpo, Luigi	<i>I primi processi campanelliani in una ricostruzione unitaria</i>	Canone, Eugenio
17	Amabile, Luigi	<i>Fra Tommaso Campanella ne' castelli di Napoli, in Roma ed in Parigi</i>	Liburdi, Annarita
18	Amabile, Luigi	<i>Fra Tommaso Campanella, la sua congiura, i suoi processi e la sua pazzia</i>	Liburdi, Annarita
19	Capialbi, Vito	<i>Documenti inediti circa la voluta ribellione di F. Tommaso Campanella</i>	Canone, Eugenio

- *Materials* – The collection currently consists of 5 materials, listed below:

N.	Author	Title	Digital curator
1	Lo Russo, Rosaria	<i>Le poesie filosofiche di Tommaso Campanella</i>	Canone, Eugenio
2	Liburdi, Annarita	<i>La sezione documenti della seconda opera di L. Amabile sulla vita di Campanella (1887).</i>	Liburdi, Annarita
3	Sergio, Emilio	<i>Galleria dell'Accademia Cosentina</i>	Canone, Eugenio
4	Liburdi, Annarita	<i>Il volume di documenti dell'opera di L. Amabile sulla 'congiura' di Calabria (1882).</i>	Liburdi, Annarita
5	De Vinci, Antonella	<i>Geografia campanelliana calabrese</i>	

- *Indexes of the texts*- The collection currently consists of 8 indexes, listed below:

N.	Author	Title	Digital curator
1	Amabile, Luigi	<i>Fra Tommaso Campanella ne' castelli di Napoli, in Roma ed in Parigi</i>	Liburdi, Annarita
2	Amabile, Luigi	<i>Fra Tommaso Campanella, la sua congiura, i suoi processi e la sua pazzia</i>	Liburdi, Annarita
3	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Metaphysica</i>	Firpo, Luigi; Guerrini, Luigi
4	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Philosophia rationalis</i>	Firpo, Luigi; Guerrini, Luigi
5	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Philosophia realis</i>	Firpo, Luigi; Guerrini, Luigi
6	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>De sensu rerum et magia; Defensio libri sui De sensu rerum</i>	Firpo, Luigi; Guerrini, Luigi
7	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Medicina</i>	Firpo, Luigi; Guerrini, Luigi
8	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>De sensu rerum et magia</i>	Firpo, Luigi; Guerrini, Luigi

Giulio Cesare Vanini

The **'Documents'** section contains various materials relating to Giulio Cesare Vanini, an author of great historical importance (1585-1619), philosopher, physician and free-thinker, who was burnt at the stake in Toulouse. This collection of documents offers a detailed overview of Vanini's life and ideas, exploring not only his philosophical reflections, but also his interactions with other intellectuals and prominent figures of his time. Through these sources it is possible to gain a complex picture of his personal and intellectual struggles, and to understand how his theories and positions influenced the cultural and social context of the time. Each document contributes to illuminating the various aspects of his life and his works, allowing a deeper understanding of his contribution to the philosophy and culture of the period. For this reason, the collection contains 223 documents that mainly deal with Vanini's life, with a special focus on his correspondence.

In the **'Testimonies'** section, testimonies written after Vanini's death by authors who had direct knowledge of the philosopher (from about 1619 to 1650) are available online.

This section is divided into four sections, each of which examines Vanini's literary sources and discusses their authority and reliability. The section includes a total of 66 works, whose chronological order, at least for some texts, refers to the date of production and not to the date of publication.

The **'Images'** section is a valuable tool for getting to know the figure of Giulio Cesare Vanini, offering a detailed picture of the environments and characters that the author frequented.

The iconography presented here is divided into 12 series of images.

N.	Title	File type
1	Vanini nelle incisioni, nella pittura e nella scultura.	jpg
2	Vanini: i luoghi frequentati.	jpg
3	Vanini: le sue firme.	jpg
4	Vanini: i frontespizi delle sue opere.	jpg
5	Vanini: gli uomini del potere politico e religioso che decisero le sorti della sua vita.	jpg
6	Vanini: gli intellettuali amici.	jpg
7	Vanini: i suoi protettori.	jpg
8	Vanini: i suoi giudici.	jpg
9	Vanini: i suoi critici.	jpg
10	Vanini: le sue "fonti".	jpg
11	Vanini: i suoi autori.	jpg
12	Vanini: La sua influenza sul pensiero del Seicento.	jpg

The **'Bibliography'** section lists, in chronological order, from 1619 (the year of Giulio Cesare Vanini's death) to 2012, all the texts that mention the Salento philosopher in various ways. The titles are arranged in chronological order according to the date of publication of the first editions of the studies.

In addition to the bibliography, there is also an alphabetical index organised by author, providing a double research approach.

This section is currently divided into the following four sections:

N.	Years	Number of files	Type of files
1	1619 – 1700	9	pdf
2	1701 – 1800	10	pdf
3	1801 – 1900	10	pdf
4	1901 – 2012	-	-

The ‘**Studies**’ section publishes previously unpublished essays (including those on Vanini's lexicon) and re-proposes studies on Vanini that are of particular relevance. In addition to a detailed history of the criticism of the philosopher's philosophy, the section also contains informative notes on the most important historiographical contributions. Special attention is given to the scientific production of the last fifty years.

The collection currently consists of 9 studies, listed below:

N.	Author	Title
1	Armogathe, Jean Robert	<i>Jules-César Vanini: une rhétorique de la subversion</i>
2	Cavaillé, Jean Pierre	<i>Jules-César Vanini: la langue arrachée</i>
3	Corsano, Antonio	<i>Per la storia del pensiero del tardo Rinascimento, II. G. C. Vanini</i>
4	Marcialis, Maria Teresa	<i>Il ruolo dell'immaginazione nella filosofia di Giulio Cesare Vanini</i>
5	Namer, Emile	<i>L'Oeuvre de Jules-César Vanini (1585-1619): Une anthropologie philosophique</i>
6	Nowicki, Andrzej	<i>Centralne Kategorie filozofii Vaniniego, Warszawa 1970, 390 p. Vanini e il paradosso di Empedocle</i>
7	Papuli, Giovanni	<i>La fortuna del Vanini</i>
8	Raimondi, Francesco Paolo	<i>Vanini et Mersenne</i>
9	Raimondi, Francesco Paolo	<i>Simulatio e dissimulatio nella tecnica compositiva del testo vaniniano</i>

The ‘**Bulletin Board**’ section is dedicated to recent or forthcoming publications, as well as conferences, congresses, meetings, seminars, etc. that directly or indirectly relate to Vanini or his philosophy.

The only document available is the one below:

N.	Author	Title
1	Raimondi, Francesco Paolo	<i>Nota introduttiva</i>

ILIESI PRIN – The body-soul problem in the light of ethics

The Archive is a project that focuses on the publication of studies, texts and a collective volume, the organisation of seminars and a final conference, and the creation of a website with a hypertext. The core of the project is the analysis of philosophical works from the 15th to the 18th centuries, including those of Marsilio Ficino, Giordano Bruno and Giambattista Vico, in order to explore the theme of the relationship between the soul and the body. In addition, ecclesiastical censures on philosophical texts of the time are also published. The aim is therefore to examine how the relationship between soul and body influences moral reflection, touching on areas such as anthropology, epistemology, metaphysics and cosmology. The Archive consists of several sub-sections, including

- *Seminars and Meetings* – In this section there is a detailed list of seminars and study days covering a wide range of topics. For each event, the location and date of the event are given, together with the poster and an abstract summarising the main contents. In general, these are events organised by the ILIESI- Istituto per il Lessico Intellettuale Europeo e Storia delle Idee between 2013 and 2015, during which ILIESI managed and supervised part of the PRIN 2010-2011 project.

The section currently consists of 14 documents, listed below:

N.	Event title	Document type
1	<i>CUREAU DE LA CHAMBRE ISTINTO IMMAGINAZIONE INNATISMO</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina
2	<i>UN VOLUME, UN PROGETTO ANIMA-CORPO ALLA LUCE DELL'ETICA ANTICHI E MODERNI</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina
3	<i>I PALINSESTI DI DIOTIMA. UN LIBRO, UNA COLLANA DI FILOSOFI E LETTERATE</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina
4	<i>TOMMASO CAMPANELLA: ANIMA-CORPO E LA SFERA ETICA. PAROLE CHIAVE</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina • Abstract – De Lucca J. P. • Abstract – Perugini M.
5	<i>ANIMA-CORPO ALLA LUCE DELL'ETICA. UMANI & ANIMALI</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina • Abstract – Marchetto M. • Abstract – Muratori C. • Abstract – Secchi P. • Abstract – Taurino D.
6	<i>I FILOSOFI E L'ANIMALITÀ: ASPETTI E FIGURE DI UN DIBATTITO PLURISECOLARE</i> <i>Stefano Gensini, Il linguaggio degli animali: sul naturalismo linguistico di Girolamo Fabrici d'Acquapendente (1533 – 1619)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina

7	<p><i>I FILOSOFI E L'ANIMALITÀ: ASPETTI E FIGURE DI UN DIBATTITO PLURISECOLARE</i></p> <p><i>Luisa Valente, Animali nocivi, perfezione del creato e caduta dell'uomo nella teologia del XII secolo</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina • Dispensa – Valente L.
8	<p><i>I FILOSOFI E L'ANIMALITÀ: ASPETTI E FIGURE DI UN DIBATTITO PLURISECOLARE</i></p> <p><i>Andrei Rossius, Il rapporto anima-corpo e il tema del mondo animale negli scritti bruniani del Codice Norov</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina
9	<p><i>I FILOSOFI E L'ANIMALITÀ: ASPETTI E FIGURE DI UN DIBATTITO PLURISECOLARE</i></p> <p><i>Leen Spruit, L'anima delle bestie nella censura romana: i confini di razionalità e moralità</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina • Dispensa – Spruit L.
10	<p><i>IL PROBLEMA ANIMA-CORPO ALLA LUCE DELL'ETICA. CHRISTINE DE PIZAN: LA COSCIENZA DI SÉ SI FA CORPO</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina
11	<p><i>IL PROBLEMA ANIMA-CORPO ALLA LUCE DELL'ETICA. POMPONAZZI VANINI HELVÉTIUS</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina • Abstract – Raimondi F. P., Puccini F. (17/03) • Dispensa – Puccini F. • Dispensa – Raimondi F. P. • Dispensa – Raimondi F. P. • Dispensa – Raimondi F. P. (18/03)
12	<p><i>LINGUAGGIO DEL CORPO E DELL'ANIMA. TERMINOLOGIA E POESIA FILOSOFICA IN GIORDANO BRUNO</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina • Abstract – Canone E.
13	<p><i>DIRITTI DELL'ANIMA – DIRITTI DEL CORPO LA RIFLESSIONE MORALE NELLA FILOSOFIA D'AMORE DEL RINASCIMENTO</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina • Abstract – Presentazione seminario
14	<p><i>TRE 'MAESTRI' DI GIORDANO BRUNO: ARISTOTELE · ORIGENE · GIOVAN VINCENZO COLLE</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locandina • Abstract – Presentazione seminario

Illness in ConText: words of philosophy and guidance during the pandemic.

The archive 'Illness in Context: words of philosophy and guidance in the pandemic' is a platform that has decided to contribute to the COVID-19 pandemic crisis. Through words of philosophy and guidance, this initiative is not limited to the history of philosophy, but also includes reflections on themes, authors and experiences, highlighting the importance of knowing the history and contexts of words. For example, scientific terms such as 'contagion' and 'epidemic' are explored in a broader context than just medicine. Concepts such as the relationship between body and soul, emotions and the experience of isolation are also explored to document the variety of contexts.

The archive consists of several sections, including:

- Anima/Corpo (Soul/Body);
- Carcere/Segregazione (Prison/Segregation);
- Cura dell'anima/Cura del corpo (Care of the soul/Care of the body);
- Epidemia/Peste (Epidemic/Plague);
- Fato astrale (Astral Fate);
- Isolamento (Isolation);
- κρόνος/καιρός: tempo che opprime e tempo che salva (time that oppresses and time that saves);
- Resilienza (Resilience);
- Timore e paura – Speranza (Fear and dread – Hope);
- Philosophical Lexica;
- Biblical words;
- Pandemic and words.

In the '**Anima/Corpo** (Soul/Body)' section, many articles have been published on the relationship between the soul and the body, exploring different aspects of passions and emotions, in collaboration with various publishers.

The section currently consists of 18 documents listed below:

N.	Author	Title
1	Alesse, Francesca	<i>Il tema delle affezioni nell'antropologia di Marco Aurelio</i>
2	Arcangeli, Alessandro	<i>Cardano: sognare gli affetti</i>
3	Castelli, Laura M.	<i>Manifestazioni somatiche e fisiologia delle "affezioni dell'anima" nei Problemata aristotelici</i>
4	Centrone, Bruno	<i>Μελαγχολικός in Aristotele e il Problema XXX, 1</i>
5	Centrone, Bruno	<i>La componente corporea delle affezioni dell'anima in Aristotele</i>
6	Chiaradonna, Riccardo	<i>Dualismo metafisico e teoria dell'azione in Plotino</i>
7	De Lucca, Jean-Paul	<i>Corpo, spirito e anima-mente: l'antropologia della libertà in Campanella</i>
8	Fronterotta, Francesco	<i>Conoscenza ed ethos fra anima e corpo nella Repubblica (e nel Timeo) di Platone</i>

9	Fronterotta, Francesco	<i>Per una misura delle passioni: ὕβριν σθενύνααι e θυμῷ μάχεσθαι nei frammenti 43 e 85 DK di Eraclito</i>
10	Lettieri, Gaetano	<i>Emozioni e amore patico in Agostino</i>
11	Quarantotto, Diana	<i>Il dialogo dell'anima (di Aristotele) con se stessa. I Problemata: l'indagine e l'opera</i>
12	Quarantotto, Diana	<i>Aristotele: la psicofisiologia delle emozioni e l'ilemorfismo</i>
13	Ragghianti, Renzo	<i>"Et au plus élevé trône du monde, si ne sommes assis que sur notre cul": l'antiplatonismo radicale del discorso sul corpo in Montaigne</i>
14	Spinelli, Emidio	<i>La traccia dell'anima: spunti critici di psicologia pirroniana</i>
15	Taraborelli, Angela	<i>Anima-corpo nella filosofia morale di Henry More</i>
16	Togni, Paolo	<i>Anime smidollate: la metafora dei muscoli psichici in Crisippo e Platone</i>
17	Ulacco, Angela	<i>Malattia e alterazione del calore naturale: medicina ippocratica e fisiologia aristotelica negli hosa iatrika e in altri Problemata pseudo-aristotelici</i>
18	Verde, Francesco	<i>Monismo psicologico e dottrina dell'anima in Epicuro e Lucrezio</i>

The '**Carcere/Segregazione** (Prison/Segregation)' section focuses on prison and segregation. Prison is one of the most dramatic human experiences. *Segregazione* (segregation) and *isolamento* (isolation) are words that refer to a situation often dealt with in literature. However, the reality of the prison experience can be even harsher than what is portrayed.

The section currently consists of 2 documents listed below:

N.	Author	Title
1	Rossi Monti, Martino	<i>Il carcere, la tomba, il fango. Sulla fortuna di alcune immagini da Platone all'età di Plotino</i>
2	Ernst, Germana	<i>La condizione del carcere: Cardano, Tasso, Campanella</i>

The '**Contagio** (Contagion)' section contains a description of Francesca Alesse's essay entitled *Contagio come contaminazione dell'antichità greco-romana*. It is a scholarly essay that explores how ancient Greek and Roman societies conceived and understood the phenomenon of contagion.

The section currently consists of 12 documents, listed below:

N.	Author	Title
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1	Atkinson, J.E.	<i>Turning Crises into Drama: The Management of Epidemics in Classical Antiquity</i>
2	Fischer, Johann Andreas	<i>Dissertatio inauguralis medica de contagio...</i>
3	Jouanna, Jacques	<i>Greek Medicine from Hippocrates to Galen: Selected Papers</i>
4	Kallet, Lisa	<i>Thucydides, Apollo, the Plague, and the War</i>
5	Parker, Robert	<i>Miasma: Pollution and Purification in Early Greek Religion</i>
6	Stok, Fabio	<i>Il lessico del contagio</i>
7	Stok, Fabio	<i>Medicus amicus. La filosofia al servizio della medicina</i>
8	Stok, Fabio	<i>Peste e letteratura</i>
9	Vegetti, Mario	<i>La medicina in Platone</i>
10	Vegetti, Mario	<i>La medicina in Platone</i>
11	Vegetti, Mario	<i>La medicina in Platone</i>
12	Vegetti, Mario	<i>La medicina in Platone</i>

The section '**Cura dell'anima/Cura del corpo** (Care of the Soul/Care of the Body)' contains contributions related to the concept of philosophy as a particular type of therapy, that is, a therapy that has as its object the soul and the repercussions of its states, virtuous or vicious, on the body.

The section currently consists of the 3 documents listed below:

N.	Author(s)i	Title
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Arciero, Giampiero Bondolfi, Guido Mazzola, Viridiana 	<i>Capitolo 11: Cura di sé e terapia fenomenologica (con allegata bibliografia)</i>
2	Miller, Steven A.	<i>Toward a Practice of Stoic Pragmatism</i>
3	Singer, Peter N.	<i>A New Distress: Galen's Ethics in Περὶ Ἀλυπίας and Beyond</i>

In addition to a contribution on the etymology of the word 'epidemia (epidemic)', the '**Epidemia/Peste** (Epidemic/Plague)' section contains various tips on how to fight one of the most terrible epidemic diseases: the plague.

The section currently consists of 8 documents, listed below:

N.	Author	Title
1	Muratori, Ludovico Antonio	<i>Del governo della peste e delle maniere di guardarsene</i>
2	van Helmont, Jan Baptista	<i>Tumulus pestis</i>
3	Ficino, Marsilio	<i>Consilio contro la pestilenza</i>
4	Manfredi, Girolamo	<i>Tractato de la pestilentia</i>
5	Mombrizio, Bonino	<i>Testamento preservativo e curativo per defensione dell'umana generazione dal morbo pestilenziale</i>
6	Machiavelli, Niccolò	<i>Descrizione della peste di Firenze dell'anno 1527</i>
7	Fracastoro, Girolamo	<i>De contagione et contagiosis morbis et curatione</i>
8	Frigimelica, Francesco	<i>Consiglio sopra la pestilentia qui in Padoa nell'anno MDLV</i>

The '**Fato astrale** (Astral Fate)' section currently consists of 2 documents, listed below:

N.	Author	Title
1	Campanella, Tommaso	<i>Come evitare il fato astrale. Apologetico. Disputa sulle Bolle</i>
2	Naudé, Gabriel	<i>De fato, et fatali vitae termino (Quaestio quinta iatrophilologica)</i>

The '**Isolamento** (Isolation)' section contains contributions and texts on the theme of isolation, examined from different perspectives and in relation to different historical and geographical contexts.

The section currently consists of 5 documents, listed below:

N.	Author	Title
1	Cadeddu, Maria Eugenia	<i>Insularidad, aislamiento, rutas. Notas sobre la Cerdeña de los siglos bajomedievales</i>
2	Cadeddu, Maria Eugenia	<i>Isolamento e plurilinguismo. Il caso dell'Ogliastra in Sardegna (secoli XVII-XVIII)</i>
3	de la Marmora, Alberto	<i>Itinéraire de l'île de Sardaigne, pour faire suite au Voyage en cette contrée</i>
4	Chaucer, Geoffrey	<i>The Prioress's Tale</i>
5	Churchill Semple, Ellen	<i>The Anglo-Saxons of the Kentucky Mountains. A Study in Anthropogeography</i>

The section '**κρόνος/καιρός: tempo che opprime e tempo che salva** (time that oppresses and time that saves)' contains contributions that focus on the relationship between two different ways of giving time, specifically between time as *kronos* and time as *kairos*.

There are currently no documents in this section.

The '**Resilienza** (Resilience)' section contains contributions and reflections on the concept of resilience.

The section currently contains 2 documents listed below:

N.	Author	Title
1	Cresti, Simona	<i>L'elasticità di resilienza, risposta ai lettori per conto dell'Accademia della Crusca</i>
2	Mattarella, Sergio	<i>Messaggio del Presidente Sergio Mattarella</i>

In the section '**Timore e paura – Speranza** (Fear and dread – Hope)' there are contributions that focus on the concepts of fear, dread and hope.

Currently, this section presents the text by Pina Totaro entitled *Paura e speranza in Spinoza. Raccolta di testi dal Tractatus theologico-politicus e dall'Ethica*.

Currently, the section '**Philosophical Lexica**' presents a contribution by Eugenio Canone entitled *Le voci contagium ed epidemia nei lessici filosofici dell'età moderna*, on the concept of philosophical lexicon.

In the '**Biblical words**' section users will find contributions by Gaetano Lettieri on the following words, each of which is described, interpreted, and explained in detail:

- *apocalisse* (apocalypse)
- *ladro* (thief)
- *lebbra* (leprosy)
- κοινός
- *crisi* (crisis)
- *preghiera* (prayer).

Currently, the '**Pandemic and words**' section refers to the following external link:

<https://www.cnrweb.tv/la-pandemia-influenza-le-parole/>

Data sources

As mentioned above, the documents can be traced back to the following main archives:

- *Daphnet*, corresponding to the section 'Daphnet – Digital Archives of Philosophical texts on the NET' (<http://www.daphnet.iliesi.cnr.it/>);
- *ATSS*, corresponding to the section 'Archive of Texts for the History of Spinozism' (https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/spinoza/home_spinoza.html);
- *AFR*, corresponding to the digital resource 'Archive of Renaissance philosophers' (<https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/afr/index.php>);

- *Prin*, corresponding to the digital resource ‘ILIESI PRIN – *The body-soul problem in the light of ethics*’ (<https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/prin/>);
- *Illness in ConText*, corresponding to the digital resource ‘Illness in ConText: words of philosophy and guidance during the pandemic’ (<https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/covid19.php>).

Structure and formats

Depending on the reference section, the structure and format of a document may vary, but in general a document includes several basic components, which are listed below:

- a bibliographical schema which includes the main information about the work (author, title, date of publication, etc.);
- a biographical schema with possible hypertext links to other resources;
- a digital edition (image or video or text);
- any hypertext links to other resources, such as the bibliographic material contained in each file, which provide further information about the digital edition of the work.

The various components mentioned above are available in the following formats:

Component	Format	Sample
Bibliographical schema	• text (html/php)	https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/ATC/schede.php
Biographical schema	• text (html)	https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/ATC
Digital edition	• xml • html • pdf • jpg • gif	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DDL (xml) • DDL (html) • DDL (pdf) • AGCV (jpg) • Spinoza (gif)
Hypertext links	• html	https://www.iliesi.cnr.it/AGB/schede.php

Metadata

The metadata of a document can include a variety of information describing the content, structure and context of the document itself.

The main metadata identified can be divided into

- **Collection** (primary resource): a category that collects and organises a set of items with common characteristics (in this case, a document);
- **Biographical schema** (secondary resource): a document that gathers the main data and information about the author of a work in order to contextualise his/her activity;
- **Bibliographical schema** (secondary resource): a document containing the main data relating to a document, useful for identifying and describing it in a bibliographical context.

Number and size

Below is a summary table to collect, for each collection, information such as the number and size in terms of number of works, pages and size of the file(s) relating to the documents:

N.	Collection	Section	Number of documents	
1	Archive of Renaissance philosophers	(Giordano Bruno) Studies- Materials Encyclopaedia (TBC)	5 1 (TBC)	
		(Tommaso Campanella) Documents Images Bibliography (records) Studies – Materials	887 34 5 32	
		(G. C. Vanini) Documents Testimonies Images Bibliography Studies Bulletin Board	223 66 75 29 9 1	
		<i>Total</i>		1.367

1.1.2 2ND CASE STUDY: ANALYSIS OF POSSIBLE USER CASES TO BE SUBJECTED TO THE FAIRIFICATION PROCESS IN THE MAKING

In addition to the analysis of the ILIESI digital collections, which is an example of the FAIRification of existing resources that raises the problem of transforming data sets that are not designed to be FAIR from the outset, this phase has allowed the analysis of several possible user cases, mainly consisting of **ongoing or not fully developed projects**, thus raising issues related to FAIRification in the making, as well as the extension of the types of data to be handled by the platform. This step has also provided cases, mainly concerning **biographical and/or prosopographical projects**, which have made it possible to analyse different approaches to similar classes of objects, thus contributing to the design of a core set of data that goes beyond the peculiarities of each project, while confirming that data sets cannot be completely standardised in a common schema, since they have peculiar data, an obvious example of which, in the case of biography and prosopography, are the properties that define the reason for the inclusion of an item in the data set.

1.1.2.1 ABCSI – Archivio biografico della cultura scientifica italiana (Biographical archive of Italian scientific culture)

Among the projects dealing with biographical and prosopographical information, **Archivio biografico della cultura scientifica italiana, ABCSI**, carried out by ILIESI, Società italiana di Storia della Scienza, Università di Roma 3 e Museo Galilei, aims to provide a set of biographical data and textual biographies on figures who have contributed, in a broad sense, to Italian scientific cultures from the Middle Ages to the present day.

The aim is therefore to create items that combine texts (specifically produced for the project) with structured metadata that map both key life events, implying the use of data such as places, occupations, education and the nature of the contribution made to scientific culture, a task that requires a standardised description of conceptual objects such as theories, fields of study, types of activity, as well as material objects such as scientific instruments. At this stage, a list of entries has

been drawn up and is ready to be imported into a Wikibase instance provided by the H2IOSC project, which will act as a workspace for the ongoing project and at the same time allow the publication of the data. The list consists of approximately 3500 items and includes, where available, minimal biographical data such as place and date of birth and death, links to some external sources and identifiers, and the scientific disciplines or types of activity of the individual. Full biographical records and textual biographies will be realised using the H2IOSC services and will have a more elaborate metadata structure.

The first section is devoted to personal data: name; surname; date and place of birth and death; aliases, name variants and a field "born" for those rare cases where aliases and nicknames are so much more common than the first name that it would be unreasonable to use the letter as the person's main name (e.g. Niccolò Tartaglia), the indication of the profession and of the educational institution(s), as well as the project's person identifier.

A second section is dedicated to the mapping of scientific activity, divided into a sub-section for the period and places of activity and another dedicated to the content of the scientific contribution.

This subsection provides a field to be filled from a controlled vocabulary of scientific disciplines and types of activity, and three types of keywords: the first for theoretical objects such as theories, concepts, laws or doctrines; the second for concrete objects such as inventions, discoveries, instruments; and the third for experiments, recipes, procedures and the like.

The last subsection, which describes the scientific activity, is devoted to the institutions with which the person collaborated or of which he was a member, divided into universities and educational institutions, scientific societies. These are subdivided into universities, educational institutions, scientific societies, museums et similia, academies (with formal list membership) and a more general 'collaboration' field for institutions with a looser structure, academies without official membership or in the case of collaboration without official membership. The next section is the list of external identifiers and sources, such as the Dizionario biografico degli italiani (DBI), VIAF, ISNI, SBN, Wikidata, while the last one contains the metadata of the record (author and DOI). The possibility of implementing an iconography section has been hinted at, but not officially decided.

As this structure should at least suggest, the challenging aspects of the project when it comes to FAIRification are not so much in the data format itself, at least in principle fair by design, nor in the relationship with not fully FAIR external resources, which at this stage, apart from some yet to be made decisions regarding iconography, do not seem relevant for the Archive that needs description of printed sources. On the other hand, the project highlights the role of identifiers and controlled vocabularies.

Regarding the first point, the main source for Italian biography (DBI) has an online version that unfortunately does not have a structure suitable for providing unique and persistent personal identifiers. However, the data creators provide a set of external identifiers (Viaf, Isni, Wikidata) that in principle meet the FAIR requirements. The main issue here is the fact that some of the entries have been derived from the personal knowledge of the data creators, usually based on primary or secondary literature, but in some cases have provided items without external identifiers. Given the nature of most of the external identifiers and the way in which the data were obtained, such cases are more common for some classes of activity, such as scientific instrument makers. The creation of internal identifiers seems to be the only possible solution at this stage.

1.1.2.2 LCA – Leibniz’s Correspondents and Acquaintances

Similar problems and issues arise in the analysis of the data provided by a second research project, the **Leibniz’s Correspondents and Acquaintances (LCA)**, promoted by the Italian Sodalitas Leibnitiana in collaboration with several Leibniz Societies across Europe.

It consists of a set of biographical records dedicated to Leibniz's correspondents, as in the previous case, consisting of a textual part divided into a biographical section and a chapter describing the correspondence with Leibniz, and a set of structured metadata. The aim is thus twofold: to provide in-depth information about individuals and a specific part of their cultural life, and to provide instruments for analysing a complex network of intellectual exchange such as the Leibniz correspondence, by providing information that should help, for example, to identify thematic or geographical sub-networks, but also to provide a kind of indirect thematic indexing of the correspondence that is useful in the context of Leibnizian scholarship. The data was previously stored in a triple store and made public in a Wiki-base instance, which is no longer available due to technical issues; it should therefore not pose any specific problems for import. A preliminary biography is stored in a dedicated Zotero group.

The dataset consists of 1630 items, which the project management believes can be reduced to an estimated total of 1300-1400.

This statement helps to illustrate how relevant the problem of univocal identification of persons is for a dataset of this type. In this case, the set of items has been derived from a fairly well-defined but still partially unpublished set of texts. The transformation from a textual function within a (set of) letter(s) to a biographical record, although prima facie (and in most cases) unproblematic, conceals some possible difficulties. The textual function, though somehow identifiable, is in fact not always univocally attributable to a specific individual, and 'codicological' analysis of the corpus, as well as the working catalogue of the Leibniz edition, does not always help. Anonymous letters, aliases, different records of the same person in the sources are among the cases presented by the corpus. Moreover, in a few cases the existence of letters to or from Leibniz is currently the only information available about a person. In these cases, FAIRification will face the problem of a lack of identifiers, while the possibility of indicating a possible identity among people who had different descriptions in the sources could be managed at the level of the project ontology, although in the case of anonymous correspondents this may lead to further complications.

Although not the direct objects of the dataset, the data in this project have taken into account some interesting cases for the object 'letter', such as the possibility of unsent letters, the presence of attachments, the use of aliases and the presence of intermediaries in the transmission of letters, which problematise an overly simple interpretation of the receiver/sender relationship.

As far as the metadata structure is concerned, it has many similarities with the ABCSI project.

It is composed of label fields declaring the normalised name, both in long form (PersonalName [Von] FamilyName [Sr/Jr], Title, [ReligiousOrder]) and short form (PersonalName [Von] FamilyName Sr/Jr), an ID field containing the unique LCA identifier, followed by a section devoted to the name, including variant forms, abbreviations, pseudonyms, previous names, membership of religious orders and possession of noble title(s).

The expected personal information includes place and date of birth and death, place of residence, information on studies and profession, and the institution of which the person was a member or employee or with which he collaborated. The following section is devoted to the correspondence with Leibniz and includes information such as the places of correspondence, its frequency, the printed source of the correspondence as well as a content mapping structured with three different classes of

keywords similar to the one described above: conceptual objects, concrete objects and worldly matter (e.g. recipes) and a set of tags devoted to description using terms developed in the context of secondary literature. Although the rationale is different, highlighting distinctions in the use of terms within the correspondence that automatic indexing cannot capture, the structure of the keywords is close to that described in the ABCSI project. The final section of the metadata aims to highlight 'connections' by indicating intermediaries in the transmission of letters, mutual correspondents, other correspondents who are relatives of the person.

The two projects described so far, despite their differences, share not only a similar structure but also a more general view of the *role of biographical analyses*, i.e. the possibility of using them *as a tool to describe complex cultural or social facts*. Moreover, they both intend to publish their dataset while the scholarly community develops the biography in detail.

It should be clear from these two characteristics that both projects aim to create and use several *controlled vocabularies*. Apart from those that rely on external sources, which will be briefly discussed below as a cross-project issue, they can be roughly divided into two different categories: (ideally) closed and open vocabularies.

Closed controlled vocabularies are generally used either for a general mapping of the field, which may include a normalised description of the consistency of a correspondence (with instances such as sporadic, occasional, etc.), or for a list of types of activities and disciplines that determines inclusion in the Archivio biografico della cultura scientifica italiana. Other controlled vocabularies, including those dedicated to the conceptual mapping of the fields of interest, containing, for example, keywords for a biography or a correspondence, need to be developed in itinere. Some relevant entities useful for describing biographical data share the same condition. Items such as institutions and occupations and, to a lesser extent, religious orders, although there is no lack of external resources and lists, are not recorded in the time dataset in a way that is adequate to the complexity of the fields and their functions, so that they cannot be fully mapped before the research necessary to complete the records is carried out. While this aspect is difficult to capture within the FAIRification metrics, and may even be undesirable, and the necessary normalisation work will therefore be left to the editorial teams, it nevertheless strongly suggests that FAIRification itself needs to be understood as an ongoing process embedded in the research itself, rather than the final or initial step of a research. At the same time, the data analyses in both cases have confirmed the existence of specific sets of metadata that are relevant to a particular research project. For example, the discipline of study or work is not directly included in the LCA data schema, whereas it is fundamental for the ABCSI project; conversely, it is still debated within the ABCSI project whether membership of a religious order is relevant, whereas for reasons related to Leibniz's irenic cultural project, as well as to the structure of the society in which he operated, it is definitely relevant for the LCA. The data from the two projects also highlight the fact that items in different research projects will be related to the same object: indeed, many of Leibniz's Italian correspondents are scientists in the broad sense of the term adopted by the ABCSI project and therefore relevant figures. Internal identifiers will help to guarantee the possibility of separate data treatment, while the reference to external identifiers will help to link different statements on the same object. It is also strongly emphasised that the data are in principle suitable for reuse, so that cross-project use is not only allowed, but in some way recommended.

1.1.2.3 The Tree of Philosophers

A more strictly prosopographical set of data can be found in another possible user case, namely the **Tree of philosophers** developed by the University of Turin (Bonino-Ruchera 2024). The dataset aims at representing academic relations in the field of philosophy by linking individuals with relations such as teacher, supervisor, master. From this point of view, the set is dominated by institutionalised relations, which are in principle documentable and do not overlap with more informal forms of influence on an author's philosophical work. These types of relations change formally over time and in different places, for example the figure of the PhD candidate (and consequently the supervisor) did not exist in Italy until 1983. The project distinguishes the specific instance of the relationship by means of the label, but the whole complex is interpreted as an instantiation of a more general relationship of descendance. Focusing on the academic relationship means having a potential corpus that is wider than that usually considered, eventually including individuals who are not "famous", so to speak. While academic descendance provides a more objectively determined corpus, the fact that individuals are included regardless of the relevance of their contribution to the field raises the problem of (lack of) identifiers as well as the question of homonymy, especially for automatically retrieved data. The data are organised in a relational database, searchable via the project website, which consists of three tables: a 'philosopher' table containing biographical information and references to external identifiers (in this context, the unique row number counts as an internal identifier); an 'edge' table containing data pertaining to the descent relationship, such as the institution, possibly the textual outcome (Phd thesis et similia), and so on; and finally, the 'label' table, which declares the subclasses of the descent relationship and carries a brief historical description of that relationship.

The project, like the previous one, is intended to be a work in progress, although in this case the additions and corrections will most likely concern the elements, while the data structure, as well as the controlled vocabularies describing the relationships, are considered to be quite stable.

1.1.2.4 Lessico digitale dello slavo ecclesiastico (Digital lexicon of Church Slavonic)

A different type of object is offered by the project sul **Lessico digitale dello slavo ecclesiastico** (Ferro-Romoli 2024). The project can be defined as an example of the corpus approach to linguistics. The data collected so far have been developed from the initial recognition of various corpora of different literary genres (hagiography, homiletics, hymnography, etc.) in different periods, and later with the use of subcorpora in the Russian National Corpus (Nacional'nyj Korpus Russkogo Jazyka). Future research on other corpora's databases is planned.

The preliminary result is a list of 78 terms that the authors have grouped into 15 semantic categories, which constitute an example of a controlled vocabulary, although they are still open to integration:

1. Basic concepts of faith, theology and morality;
2. Names and attributes of God;
3. Names and attributes of the Mother of God;
4. Names and attributes of celestial hierarchies;
5. Names and attributes of the Devil and demons;
6. Names and attributes of biblical figures;
7. Names and attributes of ecclesiastical and monastic hierarchies;

8. Epithets of holiness;
9. Sacraments;
10. Liturgical calendar;
11. Liturgical elements;
12. Sacred objects and vestments;
13. Iconographic kinds and their attributes;
14. Iconographic techniques;
15. Monastic and ecclesiastical architecture.

The main structure of the metadata is defined as follows:

- 1) the grammatical category of the lemma;
- 2) the Latin or Greek equivalent, if any;
- 3) the list of dictionaries that contain the lemma;
- 4) the indication of the original language, if the lemma is a calque;
- 5) the component of the lemma, if the word is a compound;
- 6) the indication of the semantic category taken from the controlled vocabulary;
- 7) the Italian translation(s).

The Italian translation will then be integrated with further metadata regarding the semantic category and level, its denotation and some in-context examples. The database will allow queries both on the Slavic original (normalisation is then a project task) and on the Italian translations. The digital description of this project, lexical lemmas, is another example of classes of items that can be subject to FAIRification; here the role of persistent identifiers may be less relevant than in the previous case, but the role of linguistic normalisation and domain base vocabulary is indeed preminent. It is also important to consider that the data are based on a set of sources that are not necessarily open, but whose description can be considered as part of the data to be FAIRified. Cross-references through different data schemas are then necessary. When it comes to using this project as a case study, it seems that, as in previous examples, the whole set of metadata and controlled vocabularies are too domain dependent to be simply used as such. However, some suggestions on how to define a general schema for lexicographical data can be made by generalising some of the features.

1.1.2.5 Other initiatives

Preliminary contacts have been made with two other projects to include them among the users of the platform. Although, given the state of the art, a full detailed analysis of the data sets is not yet possible for the reasons mentioned above, they are worth mentioning in so far as they present some interesting characteristics and could constitute a kind of test for the data set being developed.

The **Gramsci Project** aims to present resources on the figure of Antonio Gramsci, the Italian philosopher and politician (1891–1937), focusing mainly on a digital library of texts enriched by an associated "structured knowledge". It also provides multimedia content and a Gramscian dictionary with over 600 lemmas. The digital library is realised using TEI encoding, which allows textual markup. However, the editors have chosen to use the markup language to highlight data relating to the objective structure of the manuscripts, recording as an external annotation, referring to a specific part of the text, all information relating to the meaning of the text that requires some degree of interpretation.

This set of information has been structured in the form of triples and has been used to create an index of names and topics that can be linked to their specific entry in the dictionary (if one exists). In order to clarify the distinction made above, it must be emphasised that the creation of the index of names is not the result of a completely automatic process: individuals are not always named directly, sometimes they are referred to by means of specific descriptions, and this is particularly relevant in the case of Gramsci, given the state in which the *Quaderni dal carcere* were written, which forced the author to be cautious in the use of some names and to resort to pseudonyms. The index, therefore, although more complete, is the result of a partially interpretative operation, and this is even more true of the thematic index.

"**Harmonia universalis**" is a prosopographic dataset focusing on authors associated with the **Mesmerist movement** at the end of the 18th century, whose name derives from a society founded in 1783 by Franz Anton Mesmer, a German physician and the theorician of 'animal magnetism' (1734-1815). Despite the formal condemnation of the Académie des Sciences, the Société royale de médecine and the Paris Faculty of Medicine, the movement experienced a rapid diffusion involving a large group of people (including many physicians) and the development of several societies. The data therefore include items such as persons, institutions and their relationships. The database also contains a gallery of images, including scanned student contracts, and a section devoted to secondary literature. A preliminary overview of the data in this project shows a high degree of compatibility with the data structure described below. At the same time, it confirms the need to be able to link resources of different types to a single research project, and to identify data subsets to be linked in the form of collections to be further unified under a single project label, if necessary.

1.2 DATA MODEL CONSTRUCTION USING THE FAIR APPROACH

The construction of a data model with a FAIR approach poses the challenge of taking into account two seemingly contradictory objectives: on the one hand, the need for the broadest possible standard to make the FAIR metrics meaningful, and on the other hand, the specific nature of each possible digital object to be FAIRified, which is identified and described by different data.

In order to balance these two requirements, the **second phase** involves the construction of the data model with a FAIR approach, by identifying a 'schema' (metadata standard) to be configured on the dedicated platform and a set of metrics for evaluating FAIRness.

The aim is to define a common standard that will allow

- The management of several types of resources through different metadata templates;
- The design of templates for each of the resources, with a technical-functional description and relative exemplification on the identified resources.

The purpose of this phase is to define:

- the schema (unique metadata standard);
- the characteristics of each template (metadata list, mandatory information, validation rules, ...) to be associated with each resource;
- the FAIR validation rules;
- the controlled vocabularies for the description of data and resources;
- the requirements to be contributed to WP4 – Common Semantic Framework in terms of self-completion and semantic validation.

Before continuing with the structure of the single templates, it is worth pointing out some other common properties. The structure of the schemas and all the templates is based on the **XML TEI**. Its structure therefore allows for first level validation of both schemas and templates (where validation is provided during the testing phase) as well as single instances. Although it was mainly designed for textual encoding, which is one of the most common types of resources provided by the case studies, the possibility of validation had made it a good candidate for constituting a common ground for the FAIRification of several types of digital objects, whose use in prosopographical studies has been previously advocated (Schwarz *et al.*, 2022).

Another common feature is that, as mentioned above, resources can be organised in collections, which can have a thematic commitment, thus in principle allowing the inclusion of several classes of objects, or object dependants, or being part of a research project. Collections and projects are therefore digital objects themselves, made up of a set of resources, and therefore their description is also subject to FAIRification.

This allows both to distinguish and to combine the FAIRification of "high level" objects, so to speak, from the one directly related to its composing objects: on the one hand, the FAIRness of a collection must depend on its components, on the other hand, there must be room to evaluate the description of the collection itself.

The schema for the set of resources has no subclasses and provides information about the institution involved, the possible grant for the project and the individual roles. Roles and functions in a project are described using a controlled vocabulary derived from **MARC 21 Relator terms**. Each schema for an individual item includes the ability to declare its relevance to a higher-level object.

In addition to the project schema with its own descriptive card, the resources have been divided into five main categories: texts, terminologies, prosopographies (which include biographies), bibliographies and images.

It should be stressed that the rationale behind this classification is twofold. On the one hand, it aims at characterising the items according to the function they play in a research project and, on the other hand, with a view to their FAIRification, i.e. by identifying the metadata necessary for a univocal description and identification of the object. These two requirements have proved to be quite coherent with each other, thus justifying the structure of the schemas, and it is in this light that possible overlaps (e.g. terminologies can be texts) are justified.

As will become clearer in the following, possible overlaps are acknowledged by the presence of common features between different schemas, but the distinction is justified by the presence of specific metadata that, while characterising the resource, should help to define its function or the reason for its relevance within a project.

The '**Texts**' category is, unsurprisingly, a set of descriptions of text-bearing objects and is mainly concerned with projects that provide digital editions or reproductions of texts. The main set of metadata then relates to the description of the digital edition/reproduction with information on format, type of encoding, data curator, copyright and identifiers such as DOI.

It is further divided into the following resource types: "works" for texts such as monographs, novels, etc., "archival documents", "letters", "articles (in reviews)", "lexica" (considered as a textual object suitable for an edition, for example).

Each type of resource is then associated with one or more schemas where its description is implemented. For the Text category, the schemas are mainly distinguished by the type of source (printed or manuscript), since different metadata are needed to distinguish the two cases. The description of a printed source will require, in addition to title and author, data such as place and date of publication, publisher and/or printer, number of pages and possibly, for modern editions, the ISBN. The schema will allow the text to be identified as part of a printed work. The focus is then on bibliographical information describing the edition rather than the physical copy.

The description of manuscripts, on the other hand, which deals with a unique object, will require information such as place of conservation, signature, consistency, composition; the description of manuscripts will also cover the description of archival documents, thanks to the possibility of adding information on the archive and possibly, for example, on notarial acts, information on the institution or persons responsible. In both cases, the system makes it possible to indicate the degree of certainty of the textual attribution by stating that the author may be uncertain, or (for manuscripts) whether the title can be considered to have been provided or "authorised" by the author.

However, the type of object affects the instantiation of the schema by allowing specific metadata. For example, a letter may be reported in a printed source described by data such as editor, place of publication, etc., but it requires specific metadata such as receiver, sender, date, etc. Similarly, an article is described by bibliographical data to which information about the review (issue, year) is added. In addition, if it is necessary to indicate several sources for the same digital objects (as might be the case for a critical edition), the platform allows the sources to be described across the schema, indicating both manuscripts and printed sources.

The '**Terminologies**' category has four types of resources: Lexicon, Encyclopaedia, Vocabulary, Glossary.

The types of resources are related to two different schemas: a bibliographical schema that allows the description of terminologies as a whole, but includes metadata that describe specific characteristics of this type of texts, such as the number of entries, type of collection, etc., and a specific lexicographical schema that allows the description of a single item within a terminological collection. This schema will include information on normalisation, semantic function, grammatical role, possible sources. As the user case shows, the relevant semantic function cannot be defined a priori, so relative controlled vocabularies will be project-dependent.

The '**Prosopography**' category consists of a type of resource and schema that describes a biographical record. The data required is limited to biographical information: name, name variants, place and date of birth and death, external identifiers, and data maintenance and production data. The system will allow further (project-related) data to be indicated by the platform for the creation of fair by design records.

The '**Bibliography**' category is further subdivided into two different types of resources: special bibliography and catalogues/inventories. The first category is used to describe a bibliography created either by the author or in a pre-existing source by collecting works thematically or by author, regardless of their physical presence in a single place or their ownership (e.g. a bibliography of the edition of Spinoza's works), while the second is used for catalogues of specific institutions, libraries or private collections (e.g. the books owned by Spinoza). Both can be linked to a digital, printed or manuscript source, but are described in different ways according to their specificity: in the first case, highlighting the thematic unity of the set, in the second, identifying the relevant institutions or persons.

The last category, **Images**, has a single type of object that should allow the implementation of iconographical sections within a research project (or, eventually, a project based on iconography). Its main schema is therefore focused on the description of the image, providing information on the file type, copyright and licence, as well as, for non born-digital images, a brief description of the source, including the possibilities of using the bibliographical or manuscript schema, whether it consists of a text or not.

As it should be clear, the choice of the set of data to describe digital objects in the FAIRification platform has been derived through a generalisation (and partial abstraction) of the analyses of the user cases, which has resulted in the definition of a set of common data. However, the research projects described above and, in general, future users may be willing to provide richer descriptions. The choice to focus on a general subset of data to be included in the platform is somehow forced by the fact that the structure of richer descriptions is goal-oriented, i.e. strictly related to the specific research project's goals. Some consideration of this has been suggested in the case of biographies, but similar observations may apply to the treatment of textual objects.

Users describing a printed source in the light of a critical edition of a text, for example, may need to describe the printed source at a deeper level than that of its edition, and may be willing to distinguish between different emissions of the same edition and go down to the level of physical copies to account for possible printing variants; similarly, a manuscript may be approached from different angles: its physical characteristics and condition, the text it bears, its history.

While the TEI schemas have some note fields into which unstructured information can be inserted to further describe the object, e.g. to emphasise the indication of false places of printing or publisher, the possibility of a richer structured description will be given in another related tools, which will allow a deeper personalisation of the dataset. This wider set of data, in principle fair by design, will possibly

be included in the FAIRification platform as a file that constitutes (part of) the digital resource itself, while for the data specifically required in the FAIRification platform, the two systems will be integrated. This will allow a level of reusability of data that aims to be independent of the specific goals in the light of which they were created, while the structure of the second platform will allow the reuse of the whole set of data.

In this phase, the software development team, in collaboration with the project team, prepares a **functional document** describing the customer journey through a wireframe, illustrating **the main functionalities of the prototype software for the FAIRification of resources**.

It has to be emphasised that the customer journey, as far as it describes the concrete use of the platform, has to be considered as a relevant step of FAIRification, as far as it constitutes a guide for the univocal fulfilment of data fields across different research projects and thus is a condition for FAIR metrics to have a substantial meaning and to grant the concrete possibility of data reuse.

The software prototype to be implemented in the next phase will have the following general characteristics:

- The screens of the prototype are designed to offer an intuitive and coherent interface, characterised by simplified navigation, clear visual elements and logical organisation of information, in order to improve the user experience and ensure easy access to the system's resources and functionalities;
- The horizontal navigation bar includes several options to facilitate the use of the prototype, such as *Search*, *Contribute*, *FAIRification Workflow*, *Statistics* and *Admin Console*, together with an area dedicated to the user profile;
- Among the user interfaces, the *Add a new record* page allows authorised users to enter new records through a selection of categories, resource types and groups, with fields organised into three expandable graphical elements.

Once the selection has been made, clicking on the 'Create' button takes the user to a new interface where they can insert the new record. For each type of resource available, a template is provided, based on a predefined XML-TEI schema and built on well-defined rules. Depending on the selection made, the list of fields will vary according to the template associated with the type of resource selected. While the data to be inserted changes according to the category and type of resource selected, the structure of the page remains the same to facilitate the process.

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Example of *Create a new item* page.

It provides a series of functions for working with the record. The "Cancel" button: allows to cancel the current operation and return to the previous screen without saving the changes made; "Save and close" saves all the changes made to the record and closes the screen, returning to the main page or to the previous section; "Save metadata" saves the changes made to the metadata of the record without closing the screen, allowing the user to continue

working or to make further changes; "Validate FAIRness" allows to start the process of validating the FAIRness of the record; "View mode (icon)" changes the display mode of the record as an XML-TEI document, allowing tooltip suggestions.

Functions in the *Create a new item* page.

- The *Import new records* page provides several ways of entering data, including uploading XML-TEI files, copy/pasting code and handling UUID identifier conflicts;
- The record detail page, *View record*, displays all enhanced metadata, metrics of interest and a FAIRness rating, with options to edit, delete and download the record;
- The FAIRness page, *View FAIRness detail*, provides detailed feedback on the quality and compliance of the record with the FAIR principles, with a ring diagram and the indicators used to evaluate the record, divided into the four principles, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable.

Q Back to search

- Edit
- Delete
- Manage record
- Download
 - Export (ZIP)
 - Export (XML-TEI)

Lexicon mathematicum Draft

Downloads **0** Views **9**

Girolamo Vitali, *Lexicon mathematicum astronomicum geometricum*. Hoc est rerum omnium ad utramque immo & ad omnem fere Mathesim quomodocumque spectantium, Collectio, & explicatio. Adjecta brevi novorum Theorematum expensio, verborumque exoticorum dilucidatione ut non injuria Discipularum omnium Mathematicarum summa, & Promptuarium dici possit. Auctore Hieronymo Vitali Capuano Clerico Regulari vulgo Testino. Parisiis, Ex Officina Ludovic. Billaine, in Palatio Regio.

Il volume è composto da trentasei pagine non numerate, cinquecentoquaranta pagine contenenti il Lexicon vero e proprio, cento pagine occupate dalla *Digestio physio-theologica ad verbum sympathia* e un *Index rerum notabilium*, nonché altre dieci pagine non numerate. Le prime pagine n.n. sono così ripartite: la dedica a Guidobaldo di Thun, arcivescovo di Salisburgo e Rainaldona (4 pp.); la *Praefatio ad lectorem* (14 pp.); le approssimazioni ecclesiastiche (2 pp.); un indice in ordine alfabetico dei lemmi del Lexicon, che tuttavia non comprende tutte le entrate dell'opera (116 pp.). Le dieci pagine finali n.n. contengono un *Index insigniorum quaestionum* (7 pp.) la lista degli errata corrigenda (3 pp.) e una pagina bianca. Il frontespizio riporta due figure (un leone rampante coronato e una testa incoronata d'alloro) sotto un albero.

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Short title Lexicon mathematicum

Publication date 1668

Author Girolamo Vitali

Title Lexicon mathematicum astronomicum geometricum

Publication date 1668

Edition Prima edizione del Lexicon mathematicum

Editor Parisiis, Ex Officina Ludovic. Billaine, in Palatio Regio.

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Vita1mm	Cf. G. Tonelli, A Short-title List of Subject Dictionaries... extended edition, revised and annotated by E. Canone and M. Palumbo, Firenze, Olschki, 2006, p. 124, scheda n. 183	jpg ↓
G. Tonelli, A Short-title List of Subject Dictionaries...		pdf ↓
http://www.mathematik.uni-bielefeld.de/~rehmann/DML/dml_links_author_V.html		url ↗

Linked Resources	
Vitali, Girolamo	Biographic card
G. Tonelli, A Short-title List of Subject Dictionaries...	Study
De speciali voto quod emitteret Regularis Obediendi suis Praelatis Regularibus	Study

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Example of the *View record* page.

The results of the FAIRification analyses can then be viewed either as an overview on the *View record* page or in more detail on the *View FAIRness details* page.

In the first case, a donut chart is provided, which gives an at-a-glance view of compliance with the principles. A numerical index allows the user to quickly identify the areas where the quality and usability of the record can be improved; in particular, for each indicator, the number of points obtained in relation to the total number of points (broken down by principle: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and an information badge on the level of FAIRness achieved are displayed.

In this page, there is a link to the detail page dedicated to the FAIRness of the dataset, while for detailed data, specific in-depth information can be provided by clicking on the "details" link next to the badge. In addition, the lower part of the right-hand section provides chronological information on the record's creation, publication and last update.

Example of FAIRness level overview

In the second case, a more detailed report on the response to each specific FAIR metric is provided (see figure below), with the possibility of further access to specific details.

Search

Contribute

FAIRification Workflow

Statistics

Maria Verdi
Registered user

← Back

Lexicon mathematicum Draft

Downloads 0

Views 9

Fairness Assessment

Findable: 5 of 7 Moderate
Accessible: 3 of 3 Advanced
Interoperable: 4 of 4 Advanced
Reusable: 7 of 10 Moderate

Findable

- ✓ F5F-F1-01D - Data is assigned a globally unique identifier. [View details](#)
- ✓ F5F-F1-02D - Data is assigned a persistent identifier.
- ✓ F5F-F2-01M - Metadata includes descriptive core elements (creator, title, data identifier, publisher, publication date, summary and keywords) to support data findability.
- ⚠ F5F-F3-01M - Metadata includes the identifier of the data it describes. [View details](#)
- ✓ F5F-F4-01M - Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be retrieved programmatically.

Accessible

- ✓ F5F-A1-01M - Metadata contains access level and access conditions of the data.
- ✓ F5F-A1-02M - Metadata is accessible through a standardized communication protocol.
- ✓ F5F-A1-03D - Data is accessible through a standardized communication protocol

Interoperable

- ✓ F5F-I1-01M - Metadata is represented using a formal knowledge representation language. [View details](#)
- ✓ F5F-I2-01M - Metadata uses semantic resources
- ✓ F5F-I3-01M - Metadata includes links between the data and its related entities.

Reusable

- ⚠ F5F-R1-01MD - Metadata specifies the content of the data.
- ✓ F5F-R1.1-01M - Metadata includes license information under which data can be reused.
- ✓ F5F-R1.2-01M - Metadata includes provenance information about data creation or generation. [View details](#)
- ✓ F5F-R1.3-01M - Metadata follows a standard recommended by the target research community of the data. [View details](#)
- ✓ F5F-R1.3-02D - Data is available in a file format recommended by the target research community.

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1.3 SOFTWARE PROTOTYPE IMPLEMENTATION

Phase 3 focuses on the **implementation of the software prototype and its integration** with the F-UJI tool, the Common Semantic Framework (WP4) and the H2IOSC MarketPlace (WP5).

The software prototype, based on the open source tool GeoNetwork, supports the entire data lifecycle, from collection to publication, following the FAIRification workflow defined in the design phase. In particular, **the prototype**, in the form of a proof-of-concept for verifying data conformity with FAIR principles (FAIRness), **offers users a step-by-step guided procedure to correct, integrate, make accessible, interoperable and reusable the resources**. The design and implementation of automatic and semi-automatic procedures for converting data into FAIR-compliant open file formats will be ensured where possible.

The main activities to be carried out are listed below:

- Installation of the GeoNetwork open source tool on the dedicated infrastructure for the development of the prototype;
- Implementation and configuration of the schema (data model) identified during the design phase;
- Customisation and integration of the F-UJI tool with the rules identified in the data model;
- Integration with the federated authentication system;
- Integration with the Common Semantic Framework (WP4);
- Integration with the H2IOSC MarketPlace (WP5).

1.4 PROTOTYPE TESTING

Phase 4 has as its main objective the **functional and performance verification** of the software prototype developed in the previous phases.

This phase will focus on evaluating the effectiveness of the FAIRification workflow, identifying any problems and optimising functionalities to ensure that the prototype fully meets the project requirements.

An important activity will be the **completion of the integration of the software prototype with the H2IOSC MarketPlace (WP5)**. This process will involve configuring and testing interoperability functionalities between the prototype and the MarketPlace to ensure that data can be exchanged between the two platforms.

An initial data collection and upload will then be performed for each type of resource envisaged in the Project. This step will verify that the prototype can effectively handle the different data formats and resource types, ensuring that the system is able to process and provide the correct procedures to make the resources as FAIR compliant as possible.

All the main functionalities will be tested, from collection to publication, following the FAIRification workflow defined in the previous phases.

At the end of the tests, the **test report** documenting the results obtained and certifying the compliance of the prototype with the project specifications will be prepared by the software development team

and submitted to the project staff for approval. Approval of the test report certifies acceptance of the software prototype and marks the transition to the next phase.

1.5 ROLL-OUT, MONITORING AND FINE-TUNING

During this **last phase, the FAIRification workflow is consolidated and released**, including the delivery of the software prototype and accompanying documentation, such as user and maintenance manuals, by the software development company.

Monitoring and fine-tuning may require planned evolutionary maintenance for 40 days.

After delivery of the prototype, the maintenance and support phase by the software development company will last 24 months.

2. COMPLETE THE FAIRIFICATION PROCESS: A SYSTEM FOR BUILDING NATIVE FAIR RESOURCES AND DATA

In parallel, **a system for building native FAIR resources and data** is being designed and implemented to complete the FAIRification process.

In order to achieve effective interoperability, the **two systems will be fully integrated** through the adoption of the same data models, the common definition of the entire FAIRification workflow at operational speed, and the concrete integration of this FAIRification tool with the FAIRness level validation tool described above to ensure smooth import of data.

The structure of the system for native FAIR data will be based on instances of **Wikibase**, in order to allow the possibility of extending the class of structured data beyond the set of metadata chosen for the FAIRification system, and to determine the specific set of properties to be adopted in a research project, but within the frame of a common defined structure.

The choice of the structure then depends on its being centred on the notion of statements, which makes it possible to attribute a property and a value declaration to each item, thus having data structured in triples. This approach allows a high degree of flexibility in the data structure, a feature required by the variety of projects and objects that populate the platform, and makes it possible to specify, beyond the mandatory data, specific information through the construction of properties.

Information that is ultimately left unstructured in the TEI schema, such as false place of printing in the case of texts, or that is not mentioned (such as printing variants in a single exemplar) can be reported in a structured and FAIR by design form.

The information and data required in the FAIRification platform will be synchronised with those provided in the Wikibase instance.

The integration of the two systems allows **FAIRification to be considered as a continuous process**, not necessarily as an initial or final step in research workflows, but rather as a procedure or set of procedures that can and should be iterated. The **possibility of iterating FAIRification** is also a prerequisite for those projects that aim to be ongoing and collective works.

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APPENDIX A – GLOSSARY

The first proposal seeks to identify the different resources present in the Institute's databases and to try to relate them, where possible, to macro-categories. This is with a view to developing common metadata models. Where this is not possible, an ad hoc model will be developed.

Another option under consideration is to develop a hierarchical schema where metadata and attributes can be inherited at each level. At the top is the project or collection to which the resources belong, and the descriptive metadata can be inherited.

GLOSSARY

Infrastructure: H2IOSC.

Catalogue: general collection of collections and resources; possibility to query it.

Project: initiative responsible for the collection(s) (may overlap with data provider of a collection).

- **Collection:** set of resources (even of different categories) provided by an institution or an individual researcher; in some cases it may include resources from one or more institutions
 - o **Resources:**
 - **Single object:** the way in which a resource is manifested (transcription/digitisation/biography/lexicon/bibliography) by an institution or an individual researcher; in some cases it may have one or more authors.

Resource category: the macro category to which the resource belongs. There are four categories:

- **Texts**
- **Terminologies**
- **Prosopographies**
- **Bibliographies**

Resource type: within a single category, the form that characterises the resource (e.g. for texts: print, manuscript, letters, etc.; for terminologies: dictionaries, lexica, glossaries; for bibliographies: inventories, catalogues, special bibliographies).

Object: digital instance of the resource. There are ten:

- Facsimile
- Critical edition
- Transcription
- Dataset
- Bibliographical record
- Manuscript record (codicological/archival record)
- Iconography
- Biographical record
- Lexicographical record --> in which <entry> with necessarily unrelated elements.

Identifier:

- For the collection; digital resource or project (DOI)

- For the individual resource in a specific collection (unique code assigned to the individual resource, e.g. serial number, collocation, ...)

Copyright: rights under which it is released

Status:

- Complete (green)
- In progress (yellow)
- Private (red)

Categories and types of resources

- Texts (types: printed, manuscripts, letters, archival documents, journal articles)
- Terminologies (types: lexica, vocabularies, encyclopaedias, glossaries, ...)
- Prosopographies (types: biographies, ...)
- Bibliographies (types: special bibliographies, catalogues and inventories)
- Collection metadata (hypothetically including multimedia material).

APPENDIX B – COD FILE CODING

The following table provides a detailed analysis of the main elements characterising the COD files:

File	Riga	Elemento	Descrizione	Codifica	Note
wolpe2.cod	1	***SALT 0016397 000			Riga iniziale
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> wolpe2.cod morene2.cod 	2	0AA		Identificativo della sezione	Separatore: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Punto e virgola tab
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> TESTO INTEGRALE SCHEDA MODELLO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Testo integrale Scheda modello 		
		LATINO	Sezione archivio		
		WOLFF	Autore		
wolpe2.cod	3	PSYCHOLOGIA EMPIRICA	Titolo opera		Separatore: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> tab
		195000003			
wolpe2.cod	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 353 406 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 003 004005 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 003 → 004005 → 	Separatore: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> spazio
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4 23 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> P. 3 TIT P. 5 DED 	Pagina/e e Sezione/i	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pagina + Titolo (TIT) Pagina + Dedicata (DED) 	

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 112 • 298 • 353 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • P. 11 PRAEF • P. 1 PAR. 1 PROL • PP. 2-3 PAR. 3 PROL 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pagina + Prefazione (PRAEF) • Pagina + Paragrafo + Prologo (PROL) • Pagine + Paragrafo + Prologo (PROL) 	
wolpe2.cod	da 5 a 18	<p>0EE+to +ms Psychologia [&] Empirica, [&] Methodo Scientifica [&] Pertractata, [&] Qua Ea, Quae [&] De Anima Humana [&] Indubia Experientiae Fide [&] Constant, Continentur [&] Et [&] Ad Solidam Universae [&] Philosophiae Practicae [&] Ac Theologiae Naturali Tractationem [&] Via Sternitur. [&] Autore [&] +np Christiano Wolfio -np , [&] Potentissimi Suecorum Regis, Hassiae Landgravii, Consiliario Regiminis [&] Mathematicum Ac Philosophiae Professore Primario In Academia [&] Marburgensi, Professore Petropolitano Honorario, Academiae [&] Regiae Scientiarum Parisinae, Societatumque Regiarum Britannicae [&] Atque Borussicae Membro. [&] Edito Nova Priori Emendatior. [&] Cum Privilegiis. +cv Francofurti Et Lipsiae, MDCCXXXVIII -cv . [&] Prostat In Officina Libraria Rengeriana. -ms -to [&]</p>	Testo formattato	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 0EE → Identificativo della sezione testo ▪ +to – to → ▪ +ms -ms → ▪ [&] → ▪ +nm -nm → inizio e fine riga ▪ + np -np → inizio e fine hyperlink ▪ + cv -cv → inizio e fine formattazione in corsivo <p>(→ da integrare con file che verrà condiviso)</p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> wolpe2.cod morene2.cod 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 19 16 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0FA (Wolff, PE, 3 Ded). 0FA (More, EnE, [1] Tit). 	Citazione bibliografica	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0FA (Autore, Sigla opera, Pagina/e + Sezione/i) 	
wolpe2.cod	317	0FF empiricus[b],-a-um empiricus[b],"psychologia empirica" psychologia,-ae psychologia,"psychologia empirica"		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0FF → Identificativo della sezione dei lemmi 	

